

**“YOU CAN’T BE AN ALPHA AND A VICTIM”:
MILITARY MASCULINITY AND
PERCEPTIONS OF MALE SEXUAL VICTIMIZATION**

A Thesis By

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Abstract:

Sexual violence literature primarily focuses on men as perpetrators and women as victims, especially in military settings characterized by hypermasculinity and the presence of violence. This, however, limits awareness of male sexual victimization and upholds silence around male victimhood. While sexual assault is frequently framed as a “women’s issue,” research indicates that 50% of military sexual assault victims are men. There exists a gap in literature concerning the role of the military in reinforcing traditional masculine ideologies that impact how male victims of sexual assault are perceived. This study utilizes 21 in-depth semi-structured interviews with veteran and active-duty military service members to understand shared perceptions and beliefs about male sexual victimization in the military, while also examining the role of the military as an institution in reinforcing conceptions of masculinity, gender, and sexual violence. Findings reveal that military masculinity is resocialized among service members through the power of the military as a total institution, and further upheld and internalized by service members. Further, findings discuss how the military reinforces beliefs about male victims and victimhood through sexual assault resources which, ultimately, informs perceptions of male sexual victimization by service members. These findings deepen our understanding of how the military, as an institution, constructs beliefs about masculinity and male victimhood that impact the prevalence and aftermath of sexual violence.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

I'd say it's probably more likely for a man in the military to get sexually assaulted because you've got more guys that come into the military who, in my opinion, think of themselves as stronger, more alpha male, so they're going to be more aggressive than the general population. - Kyle (U.S. Navy Veteran)

Sexual violence has been a topic of particular relevance for the past decade due to the newfound public awareness achieved through the #MeToo movement, a prominent social movement highlighting and fighting against sexual violence. This has coincided with recent media awareness about systemic sexual violence in the U.S. military, largely spurred by the murder of U.S. Army Specialist Vanessa Guillen at Fort Hood in Texas. Preceded by complaints of sexual assault by a higher-ranking service member in her chain of command, Guillen went missing and was later discovered dead. Guillen's murder sparked national outrage and inspired the #IAmVanessaGuillen movement which allowed service members to speak out about their experiences with sexual harassment and assault in the military (Steinhauer 2020; KCENNews 2021). Social discussions around sexual violence, within the military and society as a whole, are typically centered around women as victims, while men are stereotypically understood as perpetrators only. This conversation around men as perpetrators and never victims of sexual assault is, in part, rooted in a culture of masculinity and supported by media depictions of sexual assault (Harway and Steel 2015). However, studies show that at least one in six men will be a victim of sexual assault at some point in his life (1in6.org 2021). Despite this statistic, male¹ survivors of sexual violence are often an invisible population, and their disclosure is clouded by societal pressures of masculinity. Traditional gender norms dictate that men be macho, dominant, sexually active, and unemotional. In an institution, such as the U.S. military, this pressure of masculinity is heightened, which affects how male victims within

¹ In this thesis I use the terms male/female interchangeably in reference to men/women. While my analysis speaks to gender differences (men/women), I use the terms male/female based on existing literature that refer to male/female sexual victimization.

the military are perceived based on notions of hypermasculinity that counteract acceptable victimhood.

The U.S. military is frequently critiqued for its adherence to traditional gender norms and hypermasculine culture (Schmidt 2015), which plays a tremendous role in perpetuating sexual violence. The emphasis on power, dominance, and violence that is inherent to the military foundation is closely connected to themes found within sexual assault literature (Baaz and Stern 2009; O'Brien, Keith, and Shoemaker 2015). Castro et al. (2015) speak on this connection stating, "the ability to rape and kill has been viewed as an indication of power, and the military's traditional acceptance of violence as a valid method of achieving goals may create an environment conducive to perpetuating behavior" (2). The data on male sexual victimization in the military, specifically, is limited and varies greatly due to factors such as underreporting that constrain the ability to fully understand the scope of the problem (Castro et al. 2015). While military sexual assault is frequently framed as a "women's issue," research indicates that nearly 50% of military sexual assault victims, overall, are men (O'Brien et al. 2015). This makes sense considering that 89% of the military population are males (Schaeffer 2021). And, more specifically, approximately 13% of male servicemembers experience sexual assault a year (Miller et al. 2015; United States Department of Defense 2018; Ferdinando 2019). In 2013, for example, "there were 26,000 sexual assaults in the military and 14,000 of them were against men" (O'Toole, Kilmartin, and Peterson 2014:6). The predominance of male sexual victimization in the military forces a deeper examination regarding prominent factors and beliefs that impact male victims specifically. There are few research studies that focus on male victims of sexual assault in the military and gender-specific concerns resulting from the presence of hypermasculinity in this setting (O'Brien et al. 2015). To address these gaps, this thesis examines the perceptions and beliefs about male victims of sexual assault among military servicemembers, while also investigating the role of the military as a total institution in the production of experiences, understandings, and meanings of military masculinity.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

Sexual Victimization

Sexual assault encompasses a wide range of criminal behaviors but can broadly be defined as “nonconsensual sexualized touching (e.g., fondling private parts), attempted penetration (e.g., oral, anal, or vaginal sex), or completed penetration” (Khan et al. 2020:141). As such, sexual assault as a term does not encompass a singular experience, but rather variations of experiences, making it difficult for scholars to make definitive claims about this form of violence (Khan et al. 2020). Many theorists, however, argue that sexual assault is highly contextual, and rates of sexual violence vary among different populations and settings. Even still, Castro et al. (2015) argues that sexual assault “stems from a culture where respect and dignity for other human beings is lacking” (8). This lack of respect and dehumanization inherent to sexual assault perpetration impacts society’s willingness to openly discuss sexual violence, while in turn stigmatizing victims of sexual assault. While sexual assault data is difficult to gather due to the sensitive nature of the crime and unwillingness of survivors to identify as victims in fear of stigma, available data, even when accounting for severe underreporting, paints a troublesome picture regarding the prevalence of sexual assault in the U.S. (Fiering, Taska, and Lewis 2002; Hlavka 2016; Khan et al. 2020). Indeed, sexual assault is one of the most underreported crimes with 63% of sexual assaults going unreported (National Sexual Violence Resource Center 2015). Even so, on college campuses, which are the most studied environments concerning sexual assault, Mellins et al. (2017) found that one in three women and one in six men experienced sexual assault before graduating. Sexual assault rates outside of colleges surpass even that, with research indicating that women not enrolled in college have a 20% higher likelihood of experiencing sexual assault (Khan et al. 2020). Other national surveys have indicated that 19.3% of women and 1.7% of men experience sexual assault (Breiding et al. 2014). While available data shows that women are more likely to be sexually victimized, men are significantly less likely to report

an assault which stifles an understanding of male victimization (Mezey and King 2000; Bullock and Beckson 2011; McLean 2013; Hlavka 2016; Mellins et al. 2017; Khan et al. 2020).

While existing literature on male sexual victimization lacks in comparison to that of female victimization, there are a few studies that highlight the salience of further research about male victims. For instance, Hlavka (2016) argues that sexual assault poses a threat to masculine identities through rape myths, or stereotypical false beliefs about rape, which contribute greatly to underreporting and lack of disclosure among male victims. More so, findings illustrate how male victims' feelings of embarrassment and emasculation after sexual assault derives from socially expected notions of masculinity and stigma that are unique to males (Bullock and Beckson 2011; Du Mont et al. 2013; Hlavka 2016; Javaid 2017; Skjolden Fjeldvang 2017; Robertson 2018). These social expectations of masculinity that impact male sexual victimization are increasingly present in male-dominated settings, such as the U.S. military (Belkin 2012; Castro et al. 2015; Henry 2017; Zalewski 2017).

Research indicates that perpetrators of sexual assault often subscribe to notions of hyper-masculinity, traditional gender roles, and acceptance of violence, all of which are commonly found in the military (Murnen, Wright, and Kaluzny 2002; Baaz and Stern 2009; O'Toole et al. 2014; Castro et al. 2015; Monteith et al. 2019; Khan et al. 2020). O'Toole et al. (2014) claim that masculine military culture is so pervasive that sexual assault, like other forms of violence, is normalized and perpetrated by individuals who may have not done so as civilians. This normalization of violence, and that of sexual assault, is maintained through "a conspiracy of silence" in the military by victims and bystanders alike (O'Toole et al. 2014:4). This code, or conspiracy, of silence is predicated on the assumption that reporting sexual assault will lead to breakdown of unit cohesion and signals a sense of betrayal among comrades (O'Toole et al. 2014; Castro et al. 2015; Monteith et al. 2019). This is, in part, due to the context of war that thrives off of dehumanization and a lack of empathy in order to successfully complete missions as the top priority (Baaz and Stern 2009; Duncanson 2009; Zurbriggen 2010; Schmidt 2015; Henry 2017).

There are a number of other factors that contribute to high rates of sexual assault in the U.S. military. Scholars suggest that isolation in the military, often occurring during deployments, puts servicemembers at high risk for sexual assault due to a lack of escape and a lack of focus on issues other than the mission at hand (Sadler et al. 2021). Similarly, isolation in the military encourages servicemembers to facilitate group bonds, often leading to misplaced trust and a false sense of security that leaves individuals vulnerable to sexual assault (Warner and Armstrong 2020). Finally, the presence and abuse of alcohol creates an unsafe environment where consent becomes non-existent, and the reliance on alcohol as an excuse for bad behavior enables perpetration of sexual assault (Miller et al. 2018; Warner and Armstrong 2020). Resultantly, we see high rates of sexual assault in the military. And, males are impacted as victims at significantly higher rates than that of broader society due to the predominance of males in this setting (O'Toole et al. 2014; Castro et al. 2015; O'Brien et al. 2015; Ashley et al. 2019; Khan et al. 2020).

Male Rape Myths

Male rape myths, as defined by Javaid (2015), are “stereotyped, prejudicial, and false beliefs about rape, offenders and victims of rape, keeping male rape hidden” (273). Male rape myths are based on the prevalent notion that males are supposed to be strong, dominant, sexually promiscuous, and invulnerable, therefore denying the plausibility of male rape (Weiss 2010; Burks 2011; Javaid 2015; Castro et al. 2015; O'Brien et al. 2015; Hlavka 2016). Male rape myths are present in broader society; yet scholars argue that these myths are more powerful in the military based on “traditionally emphasized male toughness, aggression, and emotional control,” that significantly impact the likelihood of victims to report an assault (O'Brien et al. 2015:359). Three prevalent male rape myths that circulate in the military are: (1) Only gay men are sexually assaulted/sexually assault other men; (2) Men cannot be forced to have sex against their will; and (3) Men are less affected by sexual assault than women.

Predicated on the idea that sexual assault is based on sexual attraction rather than power and control, the first male rape myth identified assumes male victims and perpetrators of sexual assault

are gay (O'Brien et al. 2015). The popularity of the belief that only gay males are sexually assaulted connects to the presence of homophobia that thrives in the hypermasculine culture of the U.S. military. This systemic homophobia relates back to the "Don't Ask, Don't Tell" policy adopted by the U.S. military in 1994 (Burks 2011; The Human Rights Campaign 2021). This policy allowed the military to discriminate against openly lesbian, gay, and bisexual individuals based on the false notion that gay servicemembers pose a threat to others and the belief that gay individuals are the sole perpetrators of sexual abuse (Burks 2011; O'Brien et al. 2015; The Human Rights Campaign 2021). As such, openly gay servicemembers risked being discharged from the military if discovered. While "Don't Ask, Don't Tell" was repealed in 2011, being gay still holds an extremely negative connotation in the military due to the association of apparent perversion and weakness (Burks 2011; O'Brien et al. 2015). These negative connotations often present themselves through sexual stigma against LGBTQ+ servicemembers, anti-gay rhetoric, and even physical violence (Burks 2011). Consequently, male victims are hesitant to come forward based on a deep-seated fear of being labeled gay and experiencing discrimination, violence, social ostracization, and potential loss of job security as a result (Castro et al. 2015; O'Brien et al. 2015; Monteith et al. 2019).

Similarly, the fear of being called weak and losing some sense of their "manhood," based on the view that a real man cannot be raped, strongly impacts male victims of sexual assault in regard to disclosure and help-seeking decisions (Castro et al. 2015; O'Brien et al. 2015; Monteith et al. 2019). One aspect of this prominent rape myth is the widespread belief that men cannot be raped because they have to be aroused to have sex and arousal indicates pleasure; therefore, rape is impossible against men, and they must have enjoyed it (Mezey and King 2000). Notably, this common belief of associating erections with arousal and implying consent has long been disproven (Coxell and King 2010). Rather, researchers suggest that male erection can be triggered by a variety of factors outside of arousal, such as feelings of fear, pain, or panic (Coxell and King 2010). This common myth, however, relates back to the belief that male victims are gay when the perpetrator is also male, further stigmatizing male victims and signaling a perceived loss of manhood based on implied

pleasure and consent. Drawing on this notion, participants in a study discussing perceptions about male sexual victimization in the National Guard labeled male victims with the term “effeminate,” alluding to a loss of power and masculinity (Sadler et al. 2021). In addition, especially within a military context, we see an amplified expectation of physical fitness and strength for soldiers in war (Duncanson 2009; Zurbriggen 2010). This translates into an expectation of being able to protect oneself and “hold their own” in physical battle, which indicates that if a military man has been sexually assaulted, he allowed it to happen. And, again, this leans into the gay male rape myth as well predicated on the belief that male-on-male rape is preventable if not desired. Therefore, male victims experience homophobia that presents further stigma in the military where gay recruits have been historically prohibited. Additionally, servicemembers often subscribe to the belief that men who cannot protect themselves from sexual assault are weak and no longer belong in the military (O’Brien et al. 2015; Castro et al. 2015; Monteith et al. 2019). Thus, this assumption that male victims are weak threatens servicemembers’ job security and sense of belonging in the military. Sadler et al. (2021) explains this notion revolving around weakness and the military identity, arguing that servicemembers who return home after being sexually assaulted are perceived “not as ‘heroes’ but as victims” (13).

Finally, the belief that sexual assault affects men less than women is founded in the idea that sexual violence is a “women’s issue” (Sadler et al. 2021). While most research and media awareness about sexual assault focuses on female victims, data shows that 50% of sexual assault victims in the military are men (O’Brien et al. 2015; Quyen et al. 2015). This publicity and media framing of sexual assault as a “women’s issue” leads to a lack of awareness about male victimization that prevents individuals from accepting and normalizing male victimhood. Consequently, male victims, themselves, internalize the stigma regarding male sexual victimization and struggle to identify their experiences as assault (Weiss 2010; O’Brien et al. 2015; Monteith et al. 2019). This lack of identification by males as victims supports the assertion that male rape is not real rape, so it is less serious than when females are assaulted (Khan et al. 2021; Sadler et al. 2015). However, existing literature shows us that this is not the case. Studies show that male victims, compared to female victims, have higher rates of

psychological distress and trauma-related psychiatric hospitalization after experiencing sexual assault. Male victims also experience high rates of suicidal ideation, substance abuse, sexual dysfunction, and new criminal behavior after sexual assault (Weiss 2010; Quyen et al. 2015; O'Brien et al. 2015). Within the military, we see that half of all veterans who tested positive for military sexual trauma were men (Quyen et al. 2015). So, unlike widely shared and advertised male rape myths that minimize male rape, available data paint a different reality.

Military Impact on Reporting

As these high rates of sexual assault in the military have gained public attention throughout the years, the military has attempted to address these issues through the creation of uniform sexual assault prevention programs. The Sexual Assault Prevention and Response Program (SAPR) was created in 2005 and consists of a single program to train servicemembers about sexual assault, provide reporting options to victims, and open avenues of support within the military (SAPR n.d.). One goal of SAPR is to better advertise reporting options, both restricted and unrestricted, among servicemembers. Restricted reporting allows victims of sexual assault to confidentially report cases of sexual assault so they will have access to healthcare, advocacy, and legal services, but without triggering an investigation. While the unit commander will be made aware that an assault took place, details and identifying information will remain untold (O'Toole et al. 2014; Warner 2019; SAPR n.d.). Unrestricted reporting, on the other hand, gives victims the same access to resources, while also triggering an official investigation. These investigations often take months and involve collection of evidence and victim questioning (O'Toole et al. 2014; Warner 2019; SAPR n.d.). Unrestricted reports do not guarantee confidentiality, though details will only be given to necessary personnel involved in the investigation. Importantly, this does not prevent informal group pressure that forces victims to identify themselves within a unit after official reporting takes place. And while there are explicit consequences against retaliation practices, there is no official mention of penalties against this type of coercive identification of victims. Consequently, male victims who file restricted and unrestricted

reports are both at great risk of stigma resulting from male rape myths (Castro et al. 2015; O'Brien et al. 2015; Monteith et al. 2019).

Related to male-specific victimization, SAPR initiated a "Men's Campaign" in January of 2020, which was framed as a concentrated effort toward addressing male-specific consequences of sexual assault (SAPR n.d.). However, this initiative is new and consists only of a short video series, campaign posters, and brochures that are not actually male-specific. The information contained in the posters and brochures reference sexual assault information for all victims, while only one poster advertises how male victims experience sexual assault through hazing specifically (SAPR n.d.). Considering the effectiveness of SAPR in the military, they call for a systematic evaluation of current training programs and the protocols in initiating these trainings (Holland, Rabelo, and Cortina 2014). The military has been critiqued for their lack of emphasis on sexual assault training and in addressing root causes of sexual assault, leading to the assertion that most members of the Armed Forces do not receive effective sexual assault training (Holland et al. 2014). Although SAPR is a centralized sexual assault program in the armed forces, there are minor variations in the material across branches, and individual factors, such as training leaders and branch culture, impact the effectiveness of SAPR trainings (Holland et al. 2014). Surveying perceived effectiveness and extensiveness of training material among servicemembers, Holland et al. (2014) found that comprehensive sexual assault training programs have been positively associated with a decrease in sexual assault and willingness of servicemembers to report and access resources. Despite some efforts at formalized and institutional programming around sexual assault in the military, underreporting remains high as a result of hypermasculinity and the prominence of male rape myths in the military. According to the Department of Defense (2020), in 2018 there were 6,053 reports of sexual assault by servicemembers that occurred during military service. In contrast, the same survey estimated the actual number of servicemembers who had experienced sexual assault in the previous year averaged 20,500 incidents. This discrepancy between the number of reports and the estimated number of incidents illustrates how prominent underreporting of sexual assault is in the

military. Just as civilian males are less likely to report sexual assault when compared to civilian females due to pressures of masculinity (Mezey and King 2000; Bullock and Beckson 2011; McLean 2013; Hlavka 2016; Mellins et al. 2017; Khan et al. 2020), male servicemembers experience high levels of underreporting as well. In fact, one study found that 67% of females and 81% of males who experienced sexual assault in the military did not report their assault (National Sexual Violence Resource Center 2013). The discrepancy helps motivate a deeper examination of the effectiveness of military sexual assault programs, as well as perceptions and beliefs about male sexual victimization.

While there are many studies that examine either the masculine culture pervading the U.S. military or the prevalence of sexual assault in the military, less often considered are how these topics intersect. There exists a gap in the literature concerning how the masculine culture of the military affects male victims of sexual assault and how the current environment and training in the military may reinforce traditional masculine ideologies that impact sexual assault. In an effort of addressing this gap, I utilize in-depth semi-structured interviews with 21 participants to understand the perceptions and beliefs about male victims of sexual assault among U.S. military service members while also examining their perceptions of the role of the military institution in reinforcing definitions of masculinity, gender, and sexual violence.

CHAPTER 3

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The present research draws from four theoretical lenses to examine perceptions of male sexual victimization in the U.S. military: (1) Connell and Enloe's hegemonic and military masculinity, (2) Goffman's total militarized institution, (3) Christie's ideal victimhood, and (4) Goffman's stigma. The following section details each theory and how they are employed before explaining the combined effect of these theories in this study.

Connell and Enloe's Hegemonic and Military Masculinity

Connell (1995[2005]) introduces the concept of hegemonic masculinity, which is defined by the form of masculinity consisting of patterned practices of behavior prescribed to be the norm in a given time and space. While hegemonic masculinity is fluid and ever-changing socially, it reflects prominent cultural ideals that reinforce power inequities based on a hierarchy of masculinities that value the dominance of cisgender men and the subordination of women and gender non-conforming individuals (Connell 1995[2005], Connell and Messerschmidt 2005). Because hegemonic masculinity reflects popular conceptions of gender relations at a specific point in time and exists to legitimize dominance, it is considered normative; yet it is also hard to achieve (Connell and Messerschmidt 2005). This means that the standards of hegemonic masculinity, while widely accepted, value and praise masculine archetypes that are nearly impossible to emulate. Accordingly, for the purpose of this thesis, I refer to Western hegemonic masculinity through the adherence to traits such as "independence, ambition, assertiveness, and dominance" (Daigle & Mummert 2014:259). Additionally, some of the more physical expectations of masculinity include strength, aggressiveness, and sexual promiscuity (Duncanson 2009; Daigle & Mummert 2014; Munsch & Gruys 2018).

In looking at masculinity in the military, we must first examine the process of militarization, which Enloe (1983; 2014; 2016) argues is rooted in the value of power and domination to ensure social stability. Enloe (2016:24) introduces the concept of militarization, which is defined as:

the step-by-step social, political, and psychological process by which any person, any group, or any society absorbs the ideas and resultant practices of militarism. Women

and men each can become militarized, though usually they are militarized in rather different ways because militaristic ideas are so deeply imbued with gendered assumptions and values.

In addition to the adoption of militaristic values that view military violence as effective and necessary in a dangerous world, Enloe (1983; 2014; 2016) argues that dualistic ideas about gender, such as the notion that men are rational and women are irrational or that men are strong and women are weak, become militarized. These ideas are then transformed into militaristic assumptions about gender relations where men are seen as natural protectors and women need to be protected. By proxy, men are associated as leaders and decision makers who are responsible for international relations and national security. In comparison, women are vulnerable and unknowing, whose role is at home. Militarization impacts gendered relationships at local, national, and international levels, promoting patriarchal ideals that value masculinity over femininity based on perceived value and worth. This ultimately sets the stage for gender bias against women in the military and the promotion of men and masculine ideologies that characterize the military as a predominantly male setting (Schaefer et al. 2021). Further, Enloe (1983; 2014; 2016) argues that militarization is closely tied to nationalism because it connects a community with a sense of belonging and patriotism against an imagined external security threat that demands a dependence on male protectors. As a result, military masculinity is conflated with national security and patriotism while valuing traits of Western hegemonic masculinity that support patriarchal ideals that value masculinity, and men, over femininity and women.

While there is often a lack of consensus regarding specific components of masculinity and the role it plays in society, scholars agree that masculinity is socially constructed and is heavily dependent on the social context in which it is being examined (Enloe 1993; Connell 1995[2005]; Belkin 2012). As such, there are many sub forms of masculinity that vary across time and space concerning the context of race, age, class, and even gender (Franklin 1987; Schrock and Schwalbe 2009; Cao 2021). Each category of masculinity has its own set of norms concerning behavior and the presentation of their masculine selves. For example, aspects of normative masculinity in China

promote average-sized bodies and personalities that blend in and go unnoticed (Cao 2021). This contrasts Western conceptions of masculinity which promote dominance and the importance of large, muscular physiques (Daigle and Mummert 2014; Munsch and Gruys 2018). Additionally, there are stark differences in conceptions of masculinity across time as masculine traits reflect the process of modernity (Jordan and Cowan 1995). These changes in masculinity show us the variation in hegemony.

Much like hegemonic masculinity, the concept of military masculinity is frequently contested and reconceptualized (Belkin 2012, Henry 2017, Zalewski 2017). This persistent lack of consensus is attributed to the fluid nature of masculinity as a whole and how gendered beliefs and norms frequently change. Additionally, some theorists, such as Aaron Belkin (2012), argue that most conceptualizations of military masculinities provide an oversimplified definition that ignores the complex history of the U.S. military and the secretive, contradictory nature of military training procedures, which I discuss later in this section. Because the study of military masculinity is frequently undefined and in flux, I focus on aspects of military masculinity that remain agreed upon throughout time.

A look at the operations of these expectations in the military shows a heightened promotion and adherence to masculine ideals, indicating the presence of hypermasculinity, defined as the “expressions of extreme, exaggerated, or stereotypic masculine attributes and behaviors” (Rosen, Knudson, and Fancher 2003:326). Hegemonic hypermasculinity, combined with military specific contexts, is a defining feature of military masculinities. For example, while aggression and dominance are key components of hegemonic hypermasculinity, boys and men are taught to control that urge based on “discourses of civil society” that call for “rationality, responsibility, and decorum” (Jordan and Cowan 1995:728). Therefore, violence is discouraged and controlled in society, aside from when it is necessary to “preserve freedom,” which is inherent to the U.S. military (Jordan and Cowan 1995:728). In other words, the military provides a violent, war-based context in which hegemonic hypermasculinity can be enacted. For instance, the constant pressure of war and inherent violence

permit the creation of military scripts (Richard and Molloy 2020) and warrior models of masculinity (Duncanson 2009). Masculine military scripts dictate that military men be strong, hardworking protectors that adhere to hypermasculine standards of behavior which includes the glorification of violence (Schmidt 2015; Richard and Molloy 2020). Similarly, warrior models of masculinity are created based on the militarization of individuals including the normalization, promotion, and prioritization of violence to defeat and control enemies (Duncanson 2009). This valorization of violence and dominance is inherent to the military structure and role and is socialized and standardized in military training (Baaz and Stern 2009, Duncanson 2009, Schmidt 2015).

I use theories of hegemonic masculinity, hyper-masculinity, and military masculinity as the main theoretical framework in this study.

Goffman's Total Militarized Institution

This thesis also relies heavily on the absolute power of the military as an institution, framing military personnel as actors with little to no agency. Goffman (1961) introduces total institutions, which are closed social environments in which individuals experience all aspects of life; every action is regulated, and individuals are treated as part of a group in lieu of their prior individuality. Goffman (1961:5) identifies four key features of total institutions:

First, all aspects of life are conducted in the same place and under the same single authority. Second, each phase of the member's daily activity is carried on in the immediate company of a large batch of others, all of whom are treated alike and required to do the same thing together. Third, all phases of the day's activities are tightly scheduled, with one activity leading at a prearranged time into the next, the whole sequence of activities being imposed from above by a system of explicit formal rulings and a body of officials. Finally, the various enforced activities are brought together into a single rational plan purportedly designed to fulfill the official aims of the institution.

In his description of the total institution, Goffman (1961) conceptualizes two roles: the inmate and the staff. The inmate role is played by the people entering the total institution as individuals whereas the staff are people who work and have power over the inmates in a total institution. Goffman (1961) uses the military as an example of the total institution and argues that military recruits or cadets are inmates who are broken down by staff to fit into their roles within the military. This process that Goffman (1961) theorizes is called self-mortification, which is "the process of 'killing off'

the multiple selves possessed prior to one's entrance into the total institution and replacing them with one totalizing identity over which the person exercises little, if any, control" (Appelrouth & Edles 2016:562). This self-mortification, which gives space for military socialization,² is achieved, in part, through interactions between staff and inmates where a "will-breaking contest" typically occurs, and defiance is met with punishment and humiliation until the inmate conforms and adopts a new total identity (Goffman 1961:17).

Additionally, scholars suggest that the isolation of the military allows for the creation of socially constructed norms, values, and procedures that exist separate from broader society (Barnao 2019). Servicemembers are barred from any influence or interaction that exists outside the military, and thus, the military has complete control in molding recruits to conform to the independent military culture and structure (Barnao 2019). When applied to the military context, the totalizing identity is rooted in hypermasculinity, upon which military masculinity is grounded. Therefore, experts in the field of military studies argue the important role of the military in defining and constructing military masculinity among service members with very little variation (Belkin 2012, Hale 2012, Schmidt 2015). Indeed, Belkin (2012) argues that based on Goffman's ([1961]2016) explanation of the military as a total institution, the role of and adherence to military masculinity is relatively universal among servicemembers.

Belkin (2012:4) further describes the role of the military in constructing and reproducing military masculinity, saying:

The military has motivated service members to fight by forcing them to embody traits and identifications that have been framed as binary oppositions- masculine/feminine, strong/weak, dominant/subordinate, victor/victim, civilized/barbaric, clean/dirty, straight/queer, legible/illegible, stoic/emotional- and to deny those embodiments at the same time. As such, the troops have found themselves entrapped in dense webs of double binds that confuse them and sustain a penchant for obedience and conformity.

² Socialization is an interpretive process which allows for the reproduction of meaning making. In this thesis, service members partake in the process of meaning making in relation to masculinity and victimhood.

Belkin (2012), supported by many other theorists, argues that the military, by its nature, traps recruits into adopting an idealized and unachievable construction of masculinity emphasizing dominance and the encouragement to reject the feminine [unmasculine]. Soldiers adhere to expectations of military masculinity through forced socialization, subordinated by the military as a total institution through isolation, training, and punishment to achieve this socialization. Belkin (2012) claims that this is the ultimate contradiction: forcing dominant behavior through subordination of soldiers. This subordination and forced conformity, obedience, and masculinity at the hands of the military create a penchant for competitive masculinity (Belkin 2012, Duncanson 2009). To achieve coerced, idyllic military masculinity, soldiers are pitted against one another to claim dominance and “assert one’s masculinity,” while those who fail to do so are labeled as feminine and weak (Duncanson 2009:72).

This research, drawing on Goffman (1961), frames the military as a total institution in which service members are isolated, stripped of individuality and agency, and reformed with a military identity. I apply this theory to draw out the forced socialization of military masculinity among service members to help understand the role of the military in shaping perceptions of male sexual victimization.

Christie’s Ideal Victimhood

Similar to conceptualizations of gender and dualities of masculinity and femininity, concepts of victimhood are also reduced to a limiting dichotomy. Gender, specifically referring to the simplified male or female dichotomy, is found to be a critical component regarding perceptions of sexual victimization. That said, a prominent theme found in extant literature about male victims of sexual assault revolves around rape myths and misinformation that are specific to males, and therefore more accepting of females as victims. When examining sexual victimization, it is pertinent to discuss what it means to be a victim and how society at large defines or labels victims. Christie (1986) defines the concept of ideal victim as an individual or group of people who are more readily accepted and given legitimate status of victim in the court of public opinion. Generally, ideal victims are weak, vulnerable, and do not play a role in their victimization (Christie 1986). In thinking about sexual assault scenarios,

this ideal victim is typically a young woman who is attacked by a male stranger. Because of this limiting idea, many victims who identify outside of that imagery are overlooked, given less social status as victims, and/or are excluded from social conversations about victimhood altogether (Christie 1986; Mescher 2014; Van Dijk 2009). This aligns with discussions of masculinity, broadly, as stereotypical expectations and characteristics of masculinity directly oppose these aspects of the ideal victim. Thus, the association of strength, dominance, aggression, and sexual promiscuity exclude males as legitimate victims and from social awareness. Consequently, this social exclusion of males as victims strongly affects how male victims experience stigma.

In comparison to the obstacles boys and men face as victims of sexual assault, female victims are often more accepted as ideal, and therefore legitimate, victims based on widely accepted gender stereotypes. Female victims of sexual assault, although stigmatized, are often accepted as legitimate whereas male victims are ridiculed and experience further stigma due to societal expectations of masculinity and gender norms (Davis and Rogers 2006; Munsch and Gruys 2018; Robertson 2018; Skjolden Fkeldvang 2017). Randall (2010) relates this male-specific stigma back to ideal victimhood. They argue that only a narrow category of people fit within expectations of the ideal victim, which leads to ignored reports of sexual assault and doubting of victims.

Because society typically only acknowledges women as victims and men as perpetrators, male victimhood is constantly questioned. Davies and Rogers (2006) attribute this level of doubt and victim-blaming regarding male victimization to the assumption that men are expected to protect themselves. Male victimhood in the military takes this a step further predicated on the pervasive nature of military masculinity on servicemembers' identities. Akerstrom, Burcar, and Wasterfors (2011) speak about this dilemma saying that male servicemembers must engage in balancing acts to manage these two contradictory identities by working overtime to prove their masculinity after disclosure, therefore reinforcing that need to emulate military masculinity. Taking together the effect of stigma and the relationship between masculinity and ideal victimhood, Skjolden Fjeldvang (2017)

argues that “in short, men, rather masculinity, does not embody the necessary qualifications to be regarded as victims, especially so within the sphere of sexual victimization” (61).

I utilize Christie’s (1986) ideal victimhood in this research to explain how male victims are invalidated and excluded from discussions about sexual assault victimization. I argue in this thesis that conceptions of ideal victimhood are perpetuated in sexual assault trainings in the military, thus influencing perceptions of male victimhood and the likelihood that male victims will disclose or participate in help-seeking behavior.

Goffman’s Stigma

Goffman (1963) presents the theoretical concept of stigma to illustrate a process in which a discrediting factor is used to contaminate one’s social identity and they are, then, banished to a category designated as inherently other (Goffman 1963). Although there are three different types of stigma (i.e., abominations of the body, tribal stigma, and character defects (Goffman 1963)), the focus of this analysis is on character defects. Stigmatizing character defects includes character traits perceived as negative, such as being weak and dishonest, which are often associated with individuals who are addicts, unemployed, adulterers, or gay. Such negative stigma attached to one’s identity can be extremely damaging and serve as a mechanism for social isolation and discrimination in society. Regarding sexual assault, the impact of stigma manifests as silence by and around victims of sexual assault.

Applying Goffman’s (1963) theory of stigma to sexual violence, research shows that non-victims perceive victims of sexual assault negatively (Kennedy and Prock 2018; Salim, McConnell, and Messman 2021; Weidner and Griffitt 1983). Specifically, victims of sexual assault are perceived to have uncontrollable sexual urges, reflecting immodesty and a lack of moral standing. While these judgements benefit boys and men in meeting expectations of masculinity, they also reveal stigmatization wherein victims are perceived as reckless, sexually immoral, gay, and therefore, responsible for their victimization (Weider and Griffitt 1983). In other words, victims of sexual assault are stigmatized based on alleged character defects and moral ambiguity grounded in societal norms.

This, in turn, centers blame on the victims and questions their behavior and self-worth rather than that of the perpetrator. Victims of sexual assault then internalize that stigma and may experience a self-imposed sense of shame and judgment that limits help-seeking behaviors, such as disclosing sexual assault, seeking justice through reporting, and accessing resources (Goffman 1963; Feiring, Taska, and Lewis 1996; Miller et al. 2011; Lawrence 2016).

Female victims are often more accepted as ideal, and therefore legitimate, victims based on widely accepted gender stereotypes. Female victims of sexual assault, although stigmatized, are often accepted as legitimate whereas male victims are ridiculed and experience further stigma due to societal expectations of masculinity and gender norms (Davis and Rogers 2006; Munsch and Gruys 2018; Robertson 2018; Skjolden Fkeldvang 2017). Randall (2010) relates this male-specific stigma back to ideal victimhood. They argue that only a narrow category of people fit within expectations of the ideal victim, which leads to ignored reports of sexual assault and doubting of victims.

I use Goffman's (1963) concept of stigma to show how male victims of sexual assault are ridiculed and treated as 'other' in the military by fellow service members. The fear of stigma by male victims influences disclosure and help-seeking, ultimately reproducing underreporting, silencing, and stigma around male victimhood. I also point to the ways in which sexual assault training and materials reinforce this stigmatization of male victimization through visual scenarios that utilize images of the ideal victim.

CHAPTER 4

METHODS

In this chapter, I begin with a discussion of my methodological approach for this study. Next, I describe how I collected data for this study, including aspects of eligibility, recruitment and sampling, participant characteristics, and procedures. Then, I address how I analyzed the data. Finally, I close with a discussion of my reflexivity and positionality as related to the current study.

Qualitative Methods

In order to best understand the perceptions and beliefs about male victims of sexual assault among U.S. military service members, I employed a qualitative approach. Qualitative methodologies provide researchers with a better understanding of meaning and subjective perspectives of social problems and the social world (Hesse-Biber 2017; Creswell and Creswell 2018). Furthermore, qualitative research, by its nature, “produces findings not arrived by statistical procedures or other means of quantification. It can refer to research about persons’ lives, lived experiences, behaviors, emotions, and feelings” (Strauss and Corbin 1990:11). This personal subjectivity is important in my work, allowing for participants to draw on their personal military experiences to formulate their individual feelings and beliefs about male sexual victimization. Related to the present study, a few of my participants witnessed sexual assault cases while in the military and explained how that heavily influenced their perceptions of sexual assault and male victims. The data gained through stories and shared experiences of my participants spoke to the process of socialization that quantitative methods, like surveys, are unable to show. For these reasons, a qualitative approach was helpful in answering my research question because it allowed participants to share their individual perceptions of male sexual victimization based on their unique military experiences.

The specific qualitative methodology utilized in this study are in-depth, semi-structured interviews. I chose to use in-depth interviews because it opens the research to the unique knowledge and perspectives that my participants hold due to their social position within the U.S. military. In-depth interviews, unlike methods of inquiry such as surveys, do not limit participants to respond within

preset categories. A qualitative approach utilizing in-depth interviews was the best option in this study because it allowed for a deeper understanding of the perspectives of U.S. military service members by allowing participants to use their own words and experiences to describe how they feel about male victims of sexual assault in the military (Hesse-Biber 2017). The benefit of semi-structured interviews is that they give latitude and freedom to participants to direct the conversation in ways the researcher had not previously considered (Hesse-Biber 2017). I chose this specific method because I wanted to ensure data accurately reflects the lived experiences of the participants without being hindered by narrow, predetermined categories or my own preconceived notions about the direction of the interview.

Data Collection

Eligibility

The eligibility criteria for participation in this study included that individuals must be at least eighteen years old and either currently or formerly served in the U.S. military. I chose not to institute a maximum age or restrict gender because I wanted to see if there were differences in perceptions among different age groups and across genders. This line of thinking is also applied in terms of military status and branch wherein not limiting these factors opens the potential to find differences in perceptions and training across military branch and service timeframes. Additionally, due to the Coronavirus pandemic, I was able to conduct interviews via Zoom and phone calls, so I was not restricted geographically in meeting with different participants.

Recruitment and Sampling

After I determined the eligibility criteria for this study, I moved to recruiting participants. I used multiple recruitment strategies including convenience and snowball sampling to reach my final sample ($n = 21$). I initially utilized convenience sampling through the use of flyers (Appendix A) posted on social media sites such as Facebook and Instagram. I also utilized a combination of purposive and convenience sampling by recruiting participants I already knew with prior military experience. Using convenience sampling, I found a total of seven ($n = 7$) participants. The additional fourteen ($n = 14$)

participants were recruited using snowball sampling wherein existing participants referred other potential participants that fit the eligibility requirements (Babbie 2016). Many participants were hesitant to participate because they did not want their answers to reflect badly on the military, so snowball sampling gave me, as the researcher, credibility in terms of my intentions and role as a researcher. Thus, the chain referral of participants I utilized through snowball sampling gave me access to a population that was difficult to reach through other sampling methods. Because the recruitment process took place during the Coronavirus pandemic, I was unable to recruit participants in-person. All recruitment and scheduling took place online, via email, or through text messaging.

Description of Participants

As shown in Appendix B, of the 21 participants in the current study, 16 identified as men and five identified as women. The average age of my participants was 42, ranging from 22 to 80 years old, and the length of service varied between three and a half years to 26 years with a mean of 10 years. Every branch of the military was represented, including the Army ($n = 8$), Air force ($n = 7$), Navy ($n = 4$), Marine Corps ($n = 2$) and Coast Guard ($n = 1$). One participant had served in both the Army and the Air Force. Twenty-four percent ($n = 5$) of participants are currently serving in the military, and the remaining 76% ($n=16$) had either veteran or retired military statuses. Finally, 90% ($n = 19$) of participants were enlisted with ranks ranging from E3 to E8 and 10% ($n = 2$) had officer rank in the military. Enlisted ranks are individuals who enlist in the military. Officers hold higher rank and responsibility than enlisted, but there are differences among them. One officer was a chief warrant officer, meaning they began as enlisted for a minimum of eight years before working their way up to officer status based on specialized training and skill. The other officer was a commissioned officer, who entered the military with a college degree and an assigned rank achieved through successfully completed officer training. Notably, due to hesitancy by service members to depict the military in a negative light and the constraints presented by the Coronavirus pandemic, it was difficult to recruit a diverse pool of participants reflecting different racial and ethnic groups. As a result, my sample was predominantly white ($n = 13$).

Procedures

Prior to conducting each interview, I sent the participant a copy of the informed consent form (Appendix C) through a website called Docsketch (now called SignWell). The consent form briefly described what the interview would entail, any potential risks, and steps to maintain confidentiality. Participants were able to e-sign the consent form through the Docsketch link that was sent to them via email which established consent to be interviewed and audio-recorded. Audio-recordings of interviews were voluntary; however, every participant consented. Once I received consent, participants were then sent a Qualtrics link for a short sociodemographic survey (Appendix D) that asked for basic information such as their age, gender, service branch, length of service, and rank. The virtual formats of the consent form and sociodemographic survey were chosen because they were the easiest to complete prior to a scheduled interview since face-to-face meetings were restricted due to the pandemic. Participants had my phone number and email and were told to reach out in case they had any questions about the consent form or survey.

Interviews were conducted either via Zoom ($n = 17$), phone call ($n = 3$), or Skype ($n = 1$). Each interview lasted between one hour to one hour and a half. At the beginning of each interview, I reiterated that participation was voluntary and that participants could refuse to answer any question that made them uncomfortable due to the sensitive nature of the topic. Finally, I made sure to confirm that each participant was still comfortable being audio-recorded before I began recording and started the interview.

Interviews

All interviews were conducted in March 2021. Due to social distancing guidelines set by the Coronavirus pandemic, all interviews were virtual. Considering the sensitive nature of the research topic, some participants did share that they felt more comfortable being open about their thoughts and experiences in the virtual setting rather than if the interview were to be completed in-person. In addition, the convenience of participating in virtual interviews in the comfort of their own homes made participants more willing to schedule an interview with me. Semi-structured interviews were utilized

with the help of an interview guide (Appendix E), to ensure broad topics were covered, but to also allow for flexibility in discussion based on participant answers. The semi-structured format allowed participants to speak freely about topics or experiences that they deemed most significant, rather than what I assumed would be significant when designing the interview guide.

I constructed the interview guide in multiple phases with the assistance of my thesis chair. Once the interview guide was finalized and I conducted three interviews, I met with my chair again to adjust the interview guide based on the direction of the interviews, to rephrase questions participants found confusing, and to add questions related to emergent themes. I utilized a responsive interviewing style with a flexible pattern of questioning that evolved based on the answers given by participants (Rubin and Rubin 2011). This conversational style of interviewing gives the participants a lot of control in dictating the direction of the interview. I used my interview guide to structure the interview and remind myself of my overarching research question and purpose, but it was loosely followed based on the evolving conversation with my participants. Sample questions include:

- What does it mean to be a man in society?
- What does it mean to be a man in the military?
- In what scenarios do you think men are sexually assaulted?
- How has your view of the world changed, or stayed the same, since joining the military?
- When thinking of your daily work environment, what types of people most often work with you? What do they look like? (Age, race, gender)

These questions aimed to understand the role of the military in influencing gender roles and conceptualizations of male victimhood, as well as questioning how other sociodemographic factors influences their experience within the military, such as race, ethnicity, and age. When I began to see a pattern in themes that participants introduced outside of my interview guide, I incorporated them into my later interviews to allow for further development and data related to those themes.

Analysis

To aid in being able to initiate the analysis process, I hired two research assistants (RAs) to help edit interview transcripts. Both RAs signed non-disclosure agreements (Appendix F) and I met

with both to discuss goals and expectations before they began working on the project. All 21 interviews were audio-recorded and saved onto a password protected computer that only I, as the researcher, had access to in order to secure the data and confidentiality of participants. Audio files were uploaded for transcription to Sonix.ia, an automated transcription software. Due to the occasional inaccuracies of online transcription software, each transcript was edited using clean transcription by either myself or a research assistant. Transcripts were double-checked for accuracy while also removing filler words that interrupted the flow of the data. Specifically, words like 'um,' 'like,' 'right,' and stutters were removed for clarity.

After the automated transcription was completed through Sonix.ia, I edited five transcripts to re-familiarize myself with the data before assigning the remaining transcription edits to my RAs. Additionally, two participants disclosed assaults during their interviews, and I edited those transcriptions myself and barred my RAs from viewing either of them for extra protection of the participants. Sonix.ia has a function to confirm each section of edited dialogue and the RAs were informed to flag sections with unclear audio and names of people or military base names so I could review those sections and assign pseudonyms. Transcription was completed through a total of three phases: (1) automated transcription, (2) edits by research assistants, and (3) final confirmation by me to ensure total accuracy. Finally, completed transcripts were uploaded to the MAXQDA software for coding.

I analyzed the data inductively, focusing on the data and allowing themes to develop from the data rather than starting with a theory to test the data (Hesse-Biber 2017). I utilized a form of grounded theory wherein I modified my interview guide due to the emergence of new important themes introduced by participants and through the responsive interviewing style (Rubin and Rubin 2011). I wanted to ensure that the emerging data determined the generation of themes rather than limiting my data to fit into existing categories. This inductive, grounded approach allowed my data to speak for itself and was achieved through multiple phases of coding.

The first step in analysis was initial coding of the data using line-by-line open coding. This type of coding allows researchers to reflect on the data and remain open to any potential theoretical direction (Saldana 2009). The first three interviews were coded using open coding and developed a large number of codes with some developing prominent themes. My chair and I individually coded the first three interviews before meeting to discuss potential themes to focus on for the remaining 18 interviews. The first cycle of coding resulted in 129 codes; I identified overarching themes about tradition, aspects of masculinity, and group cohesion as it relates to sexual victimization in the military. I focused on these particular themes throughout the second phase of coding, but I remained open to other potential themes as well.

The second phase of coding utilized a mixture of axial coding and thematic coding. Axial coding groups initial codes together by finding linkages and relationships among individual codes into larger code categories (Saldana 2009). This resulted in multiple sub-codes that better situated the data into conceptual categories, such as the role of tradition, group cohesion, and military masculinity. I used these broader code categories to code the remaining interviews before applying theoretical coding. Thematic coding took the second cycle of codes to identify an overarching theme and story (Saldana 2009). This resulted in three categories: masculine ideologies and experiences of military masculinity, portrayal of military masculinity and ideal victimhood in military messaging and locating military masculinity in perceptions of male victimization in sexual assault.

Reflexivity and Positionality

Given my identity as a woman and non-military member, as well as considering my own personal history with male victims of sexual assault, it is critical that I address my position and how it affects my research. "Positionality theory claims that individuals have a position that impacts how they socially construct the world. The position of an individual is informed by multiple identities (such as race, gender, and class) that simultaneously construct and reinforce individual perspectives" (Kezar and Lester 2010:166). And reflexivity refers to the acknowledgment of how a researcher's position affects their research (Babbie 2016). Applying this to my research, my participants' responses were

uniquely influenced by the combination of their identities, including their race, age, gender, and military status. Similarly, my status as a young, white woman with no military experience influenced how I interacted with my participants and interpreted and analyzed data.

The majority of my participants were men ($n = 16$) and interview questions revolved around what it means to be a man and how that relates to sexual victimization. Because I identify as a woman, that may have impacted how willing men participants were to open up to me about men-centered issues. For example, many men participants alluded to the sometimes vulgar and sexualized language used among male service members in the military and when asked for specifics they were hesitant to answer. This hesitance was attributed to it being “guy-talk” and how they would not talk that way around other women service members. To combat these hesitancies, researchers must help their participants feel comfortable by building rapport. This is accomplished through active listening and showing genuine interest in what participants are talking about (Hesse-Biber 2017). I attempted to build rapport with my participants by engaging with their stories and jokes to show that I genuinely wanted to know what they had to say. Some participants remained hesitant to fully open up about “guy-talk,” but others became more willing throughout the conversation and after reminders that the interviews would remain confidential and that I would remain judgment free. I did not encounter this specific barrier with the women participants; however, they were hesitant for other reasons, such as my own lack of military service.

Another way my positionality may have affected my role as a researcher is the perception of myself as an ‘outsider’ because I have not been in the military. This outsider status in social research can make certain settings seem inaccessible at first, but there are typically ways to gain access such as using a personal connection (Hesse-Biber 2017). As stated previously, both men and women participants seemed to be defensive of the military and explained how one could not understand certain aspects of the military without firsthand experience. My father was in the military, and I receive educational benefits from Veteran Affairs (VA), so I worked to introduce myself to participants including my VA connection to help show that I am not a threat to the military community. I began my

interviews thanking my participants for their service in order to further show I am not a threat and as a sign of respect. I also made sure to acknowledge what they were saying and engage throughout the interview to help encourage open communication.

Finally, I have some knowledge of the effects of sexual violence on male victims involved with the U.S. military, which heavily influenced my decision to conduct this research. My prior knowledge on this topic is attributed to my experience with a male family member who served in the military and experienced sexual assault. The conflict he experienced as a male victim in an institution often not supportive of survivors like him inspired my interest in this topic. However, I believe it may also affect how I analyzed the data because I have certain expectations based on my own observations with a male victim of sexual assault. This is a concern that I was aware of going into my research and I relied heavily on a systematic analysis of my data in order to avoid potential bias as a researcher. Using an inductive approach, guided by the data rather than pre-existing theories or assumptions, helped ensure my findings were not influenced by my own experiences. I also met with my thesis chair on two occasions to calibrate developing codes and further ensure reflexive objectivity in the analysis process by checking my preconceived notions and fully allowing the data to guide my research.

CHAPTER 5

FINDINGS

In this chapter, I examine how the resocialization of military masculinity affects perceptions that participants hold about male sexual victimization in the military. The first section of findings illuminates the production of military masculinity and identifies important components of masculinity expressed by participants with an emphasis on the fact that these ideals are forced onto service members. Further, I describe ways in which military masculinity is upheld and internalized by servicemembers. The second section of findings builds on the prior section through an examination of how the military, as an institution, perpetuates military masculinity and the notion of the ideal victim through sexual assault training, awareness, and resources for victims. This, ultimately, informs perceptions of male sexual victimization by victims and non-victims alike, which will conclude my findings in the third, and final, section.

Masculine Ideologies and Experiences of Military Masculinity

Drawing on extant literature, it is clear that both traditional hegemonic masculinity and military masculinity value strength, dominance, and assertiveness. Drawing on these traits, for purposes of this thesis, I define military masculinity as the representation of overt hypermasculine ideologies influenced by the inherently violent context of the U.S. military. In this section, I build from existing definitions to describe the construction of my working definition of military masculinity through my interviewees' military socialization during traditions and procedures.

This section builds off Goffman's (1961) assertion that the military is a total institution wherein servicemembers lose all sense of individuality and are completely socialized with military ideals and values. The following comments point to experiences when the power of the military is in its total institution; service members speak about being socialized into accepting any and all military ideologies, including those revolving around military masculinity. Employing this theory and considering the socialization of military masculinity, Megan, a current Air Force Reserves servicemember, captures this experience in her basic training: "I grew up because I was forced to.

You go to basic training, and they break you down and they build you back up.” Megan’s use of the phrase “break you down and build you back up,” was commonly used throughout my twenty-one interviews. This illustrates my interviewees consciousness of how the military, as a total institution, initiates their resocialization process. By breaking you down, they eliminate any undesirable personality traits and remove any sense of individuality. Megan explains they rebuild individuals, which suggests they replace that broken down entity with their own desirable traits of what they believe a soldier should be. This, ultimately, also ensures greater uniformity across soldiers. Notably, Megan highlights the element of force within this socializing process. Rather than saying she chose to change or grow up, she says she was “forced to” grow up. This illustrates the immediate lack of agency upon entrance into the military.

Alan, a twenty-two-year-old Marine Corps veteran who left the military in 2020, expands on this process adding that, “they break you down and then make all of you the same. They break you down and build you back up. But, at the end of it, you feel pride. It makes you like a machine.” Here, Alan confirms that the purpose of breaking you down is to create conformity by saying they “make you all the same” and using the comparison of transforming you into a “machine.” Alan’s use of the word “machine” portrays an image of structured conformity, obedience, and rigidity, which ensures blind loyalty and acceptance of any behavior, values, and judgements being taught and created by the military just as we see through the socialization process in a total institution. Like Megan, Alan reiterates the lack of agency and dehumanization in this process of eliminating the self through the creation of a machine-like soldier. However, Alan’s statement presents the feeling of pride that is achieved through this process of conformity and obedience, which suggests acceptance and that service members embrace the socialization process by the U.S. military

Like Megan and Alan who represent more recent generations of servicemembers, Bill, an 80-year-old Army veteran, provides a better understanding of how long the military has used their power as a total institution in creating mass-produced soldiers. Bill, who served in the Army between 1960 and 1963 echoed that, “you just had to accept everything that they were pushing on you.” Bill’s use of

the phrase “you just had to” reflects similar sentiments to Megan and Alan in the lack of agency present in the socialization process. Further, when Bill employs the phrase “pushing on you,” he alludes to the presence of inherent pressure by the military in adapting these ideologies and military traits. These phrases, taken together, describe a process in which service members often do not, at least initially, agree with this military socialization, but they have no choice but to accept it if they are to remain within the institution.

This forced conformity and stripping of agency and individual thought makes service members vulnerable to adoption of traditional military beliefs, including a militarized conception of masculinity. That said, many of my participants acknowledged various aspects of military masculinity agreed upon in the literature, such as the influence of violence and war. Antonio, a twenty-five-year-old active-duty Army member, describes this when he explains:

It is definitely like a bigger picture. If you fast forward six years and you are on a deployment in Iraq and you are not in the right place at the right time in the right uniform with the correct equipment that you need, it could be life or death. So being able to conform and do it in repetition and repetition and not even think about it... You don't have to think about it, so if you are in a war scenario or a very high stress environment getting shot at, to a lot of people that is really foreign. And even people who are in those situations for the first time are able to push through it and do the right thing and be able to perform their tasks that they need to do because they've been trained. Endless hours of just doing the exact same thing. Repetition, repetition, repetition, and it starts at basic training.

Antonio illustrates the component of war within military masculinity in his statement, raising the stakes to “life and death” while illuminating the inherent violence that influences military masculinity (Baaz and Stern 2009; Duncanson 2009; Schmidt 2015; Richard and Molloy 2020). He acknowledges the coerced socialization through conformity yet provides rationale for this process. His description of high stress war scenarios where shots are being fired depicts chaos and a level of fear, although he neutralizes this statement by suggesting that practiced procedure and conformity eliminates that danger. His explanation shields the military from scrutiny by arguing for the greater good and the “bigger picture.” Antonio frames the adoption of military masculinity as a protective strategy by pointing to the role of repetitive practice in allowing service members to “perform their tasks that they

need to do because they've been trained." This training, and by proxy, socialization, enables service members to "push through" dangerous and high stress situations.

This connection of violence and war as a rationale for forced conformity and socialization allows us to begin putting together the pieces in understanding how military masculinity, specifically, is socialized among servicemembers. This becomes even more clear when examining statements made by participants asked about what masculinity looks like to them in civilian versus military life. John, a 53-year-old Navy veteran, elucidates the defining features that set military masculinity apart from everyday civilian masculinity. He argues that:

Military men are expected to be tougher because they are putting their lives on the line to keep our country safe. A civilian, or as we used to call them, silly-vilians... their job is just to go to work and get a paycheck. There is no life or limb type expectation from them.

Paralleling Antonio, John points out the high stakes present in the military by alluding to the level of violence and war that constructs the military identity (Baaz and Stern 2009; Duncanson 2009). Because of this, military men have to be "tougher" than the average man and the threat of life or death raises the level of masculinity expected in the military.

Alan echoes John's differentiation, adding that military men cannot show fear because showing "weakness in combat can actually get people killed." Alan's depiction of fear as weakness illustrates the rigidity of military masculinity and suggests that masculinity equates to the rejection of the un-masculine (Belkin 2012). Emotions, such as fear, are often socially understood as inherently feminine and, therefore, are un-masculine. If one is afraid in situations of war, Alan assumes that this absence of masculinity and presence of undesired femininity could lead to death. This conclusion raises the stakes for service members to conform and enact military masculinity through rejection of any femininity and promotion of masculinity, which in turn, explains the historical exclusion of women and the still-present hierarchy that values men in the military.

Francis, a 33-year-old Air Force veteran, applies this rejection of the un-masculine to the U.S. military as a whole, and how the military is perceived on the global stage. He explains:

It is just this whole perception that the U.S. military is the best military in the world. They are strict and they come off as no nonsense. So, any type of little imperfection or anything that can be seen as an imperfection or a hint of vulnerability is seen as a weakness... The military wants to be seen as this masculine, dominant figure so anything that looks different from that makes them appear weak in their eyes.

The statement that the U.S. military wants to be perceived as the “best military in the world” highlights the intrinsic international domination motivations that lie within the foundation of the U.S. military. Not only does this help to explain why the U.S. military desires a dominant, cohesive image to be reflected on the global stage, but it also aids us in understanding the internalized expectations of masculinity held by servicemembers. Furthermore, the description of servicemembers with no “imperfections,” “vulnerability,” and inherent dominance paints a picture of the stereotypical GI Joes that represent masculinity rather than femininity, implied through the rejection of feminine traits such as vulnerability and “weakness.” Francis elaborates and makes this exact comparison, saying the military “wants you to be one of these GI Joes, like these mass-produced soldiers,” further identifying military masculinity as a desirable, archetypal status (Belkin 2012). In saying that the military is trying to create “mass-produced soldiers,” Francis points again to the conformity and perfection expected by the military.

Zach, a 41-year-old Army veteran, makes a similar comparison saying that “most military men tend to be alphas.” Zach’s statement adds to Francis’s argument, identifying another key trait expected by the military in regard to military masculinity: individual dominance. While Francis points to the importance of dominance by the military as a whole, Zach’s statement illuminates how this burden of dominance is internalized on a micro-level. Zach’s use of the word “alpha,” specifically, references the alpha in a wolf-pack, indicating a position of leadership and power. Taken together, these statements by Francis and Zach reflect the unachievable military masculinity archetype consisting of strength, conformity, dominance, leadership, and power in the violent military context (Connell and Messerschmidt 2005; Belkin 2012). The expectation to be dominant and a leader present in the military masculinity archetype creates a sense of competitive masculinity, pitting servicemembers against one another as they attempt to emulate military masculinity. Not all service

members can be the leader or hold the most absolute power, and as a result, they have to fight their comrades to stake their claim at dominance through military masculinity.

In his interview, Jackson, a 67-year-old Coast Guard veteran, introduced the concept of “male positioning” in relation to military masculinity and the fight for dominance. He described issues he had encountered on several occasions stating:

There is always conflict. It's all about testing. It really is. It's about male positioning. It's just like when you take two male dogs. What's the first thing they start doing when one steps into another's territory? They start growling at one another.

Jackson's association of military men as male dogs attempting to claim dominance emulates a sense of animalistic competition where human standards of behavior no longer exist. Typical expectations of civility and decorum are replaced with the instinctual need to signal dominance and power. This picture of constant conflict and dominant positioning as competitive masculinity depicts an environment in which military masculinity has to be achieved based on survival of the fittest, echoing Antonio's earlier claim about training and the socialization of military masculinity as a protective strategy in the military.

Antonio, who had previously pointed to the importance of training and conformity in regard to the “bigger picture” in the military, explains that male positioning and forced performance of military masculinity takes place on a daily basis. Of this, he said:

I feel like being a male in the military you have to outperform everybody. Like you feel that you have to be the most physically and shaped person, you have to be able to do the most pushups, you have to run the fastest, you have to do the most sit-ups, you have to look a certain way, maybe talk a certain way. You have to be super mean at times, but then you have to be super like A-type personality.

Antonio recognizes the need to perform both physical and social aspects of military masculinity based on pressure and competition. Not only does he describe the importance for physical fitness and aesthetic, but he also mentions that you must “talk a certain way,” “be super mean,” and have an “A-type personality.” When asked to elaborate on what he meant by A-type personality, Antonio's response was “super masculine, an authority figure, willing to make decisions.” Type A personalities and military masculinity share characteristics such as competitiveness, aggression, and ambition

(Baaz and Stern 2009; Duncanson 2009; Belkin 2012). Antonio's own understanding of the expected standard of behavior reflects the internalization resulting from the socialization of military masculinity. He uses these attributes to explain the role of a "male in the military," thus utilizing military masculinity as a guiding concept for his behavior and thought processes as a service member. This sentiment was echoed by many other participants, who also added that fellow servicemembers who failed to meet these standards of male behavior were harassed and stigmatized, experiencing ostracization and ridicule based on a perceived "other-ness" (Goffman 1963; Davis and Rogers 2006; Munsch and Gruys 2018; Robertson 2018). In this way, we see how military masculinity is internalized and reinforced through group pressure and accountability.

This leads into the final way in which the forced performance of military masculinity and male positioning takes place: hazing. The practice, or tradition, of hazing was present in all of my participant interviews. Hazing practices are reflective of military masculinity in that they force a performance of arbitrary masculinity to prove oneself through the glorification of violence and domination disguised as a norm. Hazing, which is inherently violent and often crosses the line of physical and sexual abuse, is based on justifications of tradition (Monteith et al. 2019). Service members hold each other accountable for military masculinity enacted through hazing practices that authorize violence, dominance, and humiliation. While some participants refused to elaborate on hazing practices they experienced, hesitant to break their code of silence, they did emphasize the presence and importance of hazing.

Zach, previously introduced, touches on the normalization of hazing, his perspective of what constitutes violence, and how these practices are ingrained in silence. He explains:

From the day you start to the day you end, there are traditions for every point in your time there. Lots of hazing still, too. And those were all part of the traditions. And nobody talked about it because, I mean, I still don't even mind, it wasn't like it was life threatening.

When he says "nobody talked about it" because "it wasn't... life threatening" he minimizes the violence and abuse present in these rituals while, simultaneously, normalizing the silencing of hazing, coding it as something that is not talked about, but part of his daily life. Zach continues to normalize

and minimize these practices by stating they were not life threatening, while, in fact, they consistently centered around a high level of bodily danger. Zach speaks about these dangerous and violent practices, including those he was personally subjected to, later in this thesis.

Many other participants labeled these traditions as a “rite of passage” including Thomas, a 42-year-old retired Marine. Thomas emphasized that hazing “was part of a rite of passage, and no one was excluded from it.” This reiterates the consistent coercion of military masculinity that suggests that participation was experienced as mandatory and enforced to meet an arbitrary status. Similarly, when asked if service members had to participate in hazing, John, a 53-year-old Navy veteran, answered that “it’s absolutely expected. Nobody ever didn’t do it. And if you didn’t, you weren’t going to last on submarines. If you opted out, you would not stay in the command very long.” When asked to elaborate, he finished by explaining, “if you said no, I am not going to do that, they would find a way to transfer you somewhere else outside of submarines.” John’s claim about the formal repercussions for not participating in hazing reflect an effort to enforce compliance and silence or rid servicemembers who oppose military ideologies and traditions. These statements, taken together, speak to the loss of agency in the military, which are replaced by group pressure and socialized military ideologies. The takeaway is clear: conform or face consequences.

Inherent violence, domination, and humiliation are the foundation of hazing practices that achieve military masculinity. Although Zach emphasized that hazing practices were not “life threatening” above, he goes on to summarize his own personal experience, verbalized under the veil of his laughter.

So, some of the traditions would be on your last deployment you were hazed in some manner. One of our guys was tossed off the side of a hill down this giant clay hill, so he was just covered in this red clay. I was tied to a tree. The night before, they kidnapped me while I was asleep and tied me to a tree. We had another guy that was tied up in the latrines with the showers going the whole time for his last night. One of our guys was tied up in the out-house with the porta-potties and we tied it up and kicked it over, and we didn’t let him out until the next day. (Laughing).

Zach’s experience illuminates all of the components of violent hazing practices and suggests that while older servicemembers were sometimes subjected to hazing, younger recruits were more often

targeted when completing various military milestones. These traditions forced upon younger and inexperienced recruits were perpetrated by seasoned members as a show of dominance and cloaked under tradition. Zach's laughter while describing his experience illustrates the non-verbal queue of how hazing traditions were so normalized and engrained that it felt natural for him to laugh while detailing his personal and violent recollections.

Humiliation, as a form of entertainment, is a common hazing practice as summed up by Andrew, a 52-year-old Navy veteran. He explains:

So, you'd wake up at three o'clock in the morning and you go out there [deck of the ship] and you get dressed in your clothes backwards and inside out. So, you'd have your pants on inside out first and then your underwear inside out after that. And you'd crawl around the nonskid deck for hours on end. You go out there and keep them [higher-ranking] entertained. You'd sing songs and humiliation and that. And then you drink some truth serum and suck the cherry out of the royal baby's belly, who happened to be the fattest guy on a boat. So, they'd throw some lard on his belly and a cherry and you have to go in there and suck it out. There's some really gross stuff, but after you got through that you were like hey, I just crossed the line...So, you earned your stay.

These examples clearly illustrate the use of humiliation as a form of dominance. Andrew's accepted humiliation in order to "keep them [the higher-ranking] entertained," exemplifies low-ranking subordination to uphold the dominance of the higher ranks as they remove societal standards of acceptable behavior. The forced act of using your mouth to suck a cherry out of the bellybutton of another who has been lubricated with lard leaves a lasting impression of sexualized male on male humiliation based on prevalent homophobia and gay male rape myths present in the military (Burks 2011; Castro et al. 2015; O'Brien et al. 2015; Monteith et al. 2019). Andrew's recollection that the "fattest guy on the boat" was singled out for additional humiliation and bodily violation provides a juxtaposition against Antonio's claim about the importance of physical prowess in the military. This sends a message that you must fit those stereotypical physical attributes of masculinity to protect yourself from further humiliation.

Regardless of the societal assumption that hazing is formally prohibited, and thus, not sanctioned by military leaders, it is in fact an active tool steeped in tradition. The authorized communal practice of normalizing and glorifying predatory hazing violence through military

masculinity and internalized by servicemembers as commonplace, further perpetuates an ongoing cycle of violence and domination, which will inevitably impact future generations of servicemembers. Thus, there is no choice but to adhere and enact military masculinity or you will face consequences such as social ostracization and stigma, as well as potential loss of job security (Goffman 1963).

This section details how the military, as a total institution, forces military masculine ideologies through hazing and experiences of resocialization. The pressure and expectations associated with the performance of military masculinity are internalized by service members, who then hold each other accountable through male positioning and practices such as hazing. Justified by tradition and steeped in military norms, military masculinity serves as a tool to perpetuate violence, such as sexual assault.

Portrayal of Military Masculinity and Ideal Victimhood in Military Messaging

This thesis draws on the context of sexual assault in the military as a platform for understanding the ways military masculinity functions and is reified. During discussions of military sexual assault materials in my interviews, three prominent themes arose. First, the prevalence and scope of the problem regarding sexual assault in the military is minimized and ignored. Next, training programs draw on stereotypical male-on-female sexual assault scenarios in which features of ideal victimhood are reinforced and perpetuated. Finally, military sexual assault resources often have punitive effects for victims leading to silencing via lack of disclosure and help-seeking behaviors by victims.

Military sexual victimization, including both male and female victims, is a topic that many of my participants showed hesitancy in discussing. Not only was there an overwhelming sense of discomfort when we reached this part of the interviews, but many participants approached the questions with caution as if they were sharing deeply entrenched secrets to an outsider. This widely shared sense of hesitancy suggests that servicemembers may feel the need to remain silent about sexual assault to protect the military, more so than typical silence motivated by discomfort outside of the military (O'Toole et al. 2014; Castro et al. 2015; Monteith et al. 2019). This was confirmed as some

participants became more forthcoming. A belief shared by many concerned the silence around sexual assault in the military similar to the silence around hazing, which makes sense as many victims are sexually assaulted under the guise of hazing (SAPR n.d.). Specifically, there was a strongly held belief that sexual assault is often covered up by the military to protect its public image of order, cohesiveness, and strength. When asked about how a sexual assault case would be handled in the military, John, previously introduced as a Navy veteran in his fifties, shared that, “they absolutely would do everything they could to hide it, to cover it up.” When asked why, he elaborated that “because that would hurt the command. They would make the CO [commanding officer] and everybody below him look bad because this happened on their watch.” Likewise, Rosa, a 38-year-old woman Army veteran who now works for the Office of Veteran Affairs, agreed with this statement, adding that, “a lot of it is brushed under the carpet. We don’t want that; we don’t want that type of publicity.” In these statements, John and Rosa allude to an institutional effort to silence victims of sexual assault to protect the military reputation. This institutional effort to silence victims of sexual assault for the sake of their reputation showcases how the military, as an institution, subscribes to military masculinity valuing dominance, perfection, and normalizing violence. John’s argument that sexual assault cases would “hurt the command,” speaks to the importance of this masculine image held by the military in order to maintain hierarchy and dominance on a public stage. The military is prioritized so much that systemic sexual violence is covered up to fit that hypermasculine narrative concerning the strength and stability of the U.S. military on the global stage, as mentioned earlier.

Sean, a 46-year-old male Army veteran, also spoke about the institutional efforts to cover cases of sexual assault. Specifically, he explained how the institutional effort to maintain this perfectly curated image is passed on to individual servicemembers saying, “I would say that there is kind of a hidden code that, you know, you may know what’s going on, but you won’t say shit about it. Because it’s like you’re coming and saying that you’re breaking the code.” This systematic code of silence encourages the perpetration of sexual violence because the fear of consequences is removed. This, in turn, promotes military masculinity as it normalizes widespread violence among servicemembers

hidden beneath a culture of silence and ignorance. This sentiment further highlights the ways in which conformity and group trust and cohesion is prioritized above criminality and justice (Castro et al. 2015). Servicemembers are expected to follow a “hidden code” that signals military masculinity through the preservation of commonplace violence, while in turn supporting efforts of enacting military masculinity through the rejection of perceived femininity and weakness (victims) (O’Toole et al. 2014; Castro et al. 2015; Monteith et al. 2019).

In addition, this pattern of turning a blind eye has additional repercussions related to how seriously training is taken by servicemembers. Across all branches, participants painted a clear picture regarding sexual assault training curriculum and its effectiveness. These trainings, conducted virtually on an annual basis, usually lasted between one and two hours total for the year. The material introduces sexual assault statistics, potential warning signs, different scenarios, and national resources available (SAPR n.d.). However, discussion about SAPR training materials with service members reveals an impersonal, broad curriculum that is non-inclusive and promotes features of the ideal victim framework, signaling military masculinity through the framing of victimhood as inherently feminine and not an experience shared by service members.³

When asked about the perceived importance of sexual assault prevention programs in the military, many participants alluded to an out of sight, out of mind mentality. They did not perceive sexual violence to be an issue; therefore, they did not perceive training to be important either. Fabian, a 35-year-old retired Air Force captain, described his memory of sexual assault training saying, “the training was kind of insignificant, so I can’t really remember.” While Fabian is describing his personal memory of sexual assault training and his own perception about its effectiveness, his use of the word “insignificant” implies a lack of emphasis for training procedures by the military, which makes the content not memorable. The military’s failure in promoting and delivering a comprehensive and impactful training curriculum to service members affects the degree in which sexual assault is judged

³ Taking participant comments about SAPR into consideration, I reviewed SAPR materials to understand examples given, but I did not complete a systematic analysis of these materials.

as an issue by service members, impacting their relationship to the material and efforts to take training seriously (Holland et al. 2014).

Francis, previously introduced, shows how the inadequacy of training materials and a failure to promote these trainings resulted in the attitude that participation in sexual assault training programs is something to check a box, rather than to actually learn. He said that, especially the online trainings, was completed with minimal effort like “okay, let me play this in the background while I’m sending out some emails. That is, unfortunately, so common. But that’s the reality.” Francis’s claim helps to clarify the relationship between a lack of institutional emphasis on training to individual efforts to learn the material. Fabian and Francis’ statements show the relationship between systematic silence and cover-ups surrounding sexual violence in the military, a lack of institutional emphasis in sexual assault training, and how that relates to a pattern of checking a box when it comes to sexual assault prevention requirements by individual servicemembers. This helps to confirm that the institutional effort to enforce silence around sexual violence and inadequate training lends a hand in creating a lazes-faire attitude about prevention and awareness efforts.

Along with this lax attitude about sexual assault training in the military, we also see a failure of sexual assault program materials to adequately represent a diverse pool of victim identities supported by current statistics (Brieding et al. 2014; Mellins et al. 2017; Khan et al. 2020). Instead, characteristics of the ideal victim are perpetuated by identifying vulnerable women as victims of sexual assault. This is supported by notions of military masculinity that suggest that military males cannot be dominated and can defend themselves against any assault, unlike women (Baaz and Stern 2009; Duncanson 2009). For example, interviewees widely discuss training scenarios that only depict women victims and men perpetrators. I asked participants in my interviews to describe the first images that come to their minds when they hear about sexual assault, including perpetrator and victim characteristics as well as situations that sexual assault occurs. Francis referred to sexual assault training scenarios included in the Air Force, stating that:

Most times, I would say, like at least the way that it’s promoted [in the Air Force] is there is usually this creepy looking guy who is in a bar and just tries to take advantage of a

woman and her friends. And he just sort of talks to her and makes it look like they are together and then her friends go off and then he ends up assaulting her after taking her home because she's too drunk to really understand what is going on. So, when I hear sexual assault, that's what I mainly go to because that's pretty much what I've seen a lot more of.

This depiction of sexual assault is reminiscent of the ideal victim because it showcases a helpless, vulnerable woman who is taken advantage of by a bigger, "creepy" man. And while this scenario certainly exists in the real world, it is not the only sexual assault narrative that exists (Mellins et al. 2017). However, many participants explained that this is the only scenario that exists in their training programs with minor variation. This can, in part, be attributed to the role of socialization and the ways in which people believe what they are taught and shown, as exhibited by Francis's use of the phrase "that's what I mainly go to because that's pretty much what I've seen a lot more of". This narrow set of sexual assault scenarios implicitly teach servicemembers what sexual assault victimization looks like, while discrediting other victim narratives and reaffirming rape myths (Weiss 2010; Javaid 2015).

Carlos, a 28-year-old active-duty Air Force member, describes the situations he has seen in different training videos and says, "of course it's always the same scenario. A woman goes out with friends for drinks. That's how it always starts." Sean adds to this description saying, "most of the training, as I recall, was about male-on-female." Carlos and Sean, in their examples, point to the victim/perpetrator relationship that reflects the ideal victim. The lack of variation in training scenarios reaffirms the belief in the ideal victim through the consistent depiction of one single perspective of sexual assault: a strong man assaulting a weak woman. The discussions by Carlos and Sean, taken together, mirror the scenario Francis offered, showing how these limited scenarios impact perceptions of sexual assault. This repetitive trope not only limits the acceptable gender of victims, but also invalidates the experiences that fall outside of this specific mold. These scenarios that are regurgitated in training programs over and over reinforce the belief that sexual assault victims are women, not men. This makes it nearly impossible for male victims in the military to be given the appropriate recognition and respect when service members are not trained to do so. This proves to be additionally important when considering reporting implications as sexual assault programs and

resources significantly impact how likely victims are to report an assault (Coulter et al. 2017; Du Mont et al. 2013).

Sheila, a 27-year-old National Guard member who has served in both the Air Force and the Army, reflects on the importance of sexual assault training videos in diversifying victim identities. She explains that while training programs mention that males can also be victimized, it is typically glossed over before returning back to solely female-as-victim training scenarios. When asked if she believes that affects how servicemembers perceive male victims she answered:

One thousand percent. I think that's the easiest place to start. Not making it a norm, but understanding that it happens. Especially because you go through these PowerPoint slides of like 'here's the stats, here's what you do, here's why it matters, blah, blah, blah.' And then, at the end, you're theoretically applying those things you learn to scenarios. So, if you say, 'one out of every X males is sexually assaulted,' but then you get to the case study situation where you're applying all this stuff and it's all females, you don't remember that stat. You're just like 'okay, it's females who are getting sexually assaulted by males or other women.'

Sheila illustrates the importance of inclusive sexual assault training programs by discussing the importance of visually seeing something in the process of learning, understanding, and remembering. When you are only seeing women as sexual assault victims, that is what is learned and understood as the norm even if you are being told otherwise. When Sheila describes how hearing statistics about male victims is counteracted when only female victims are depicted visually, she is pointing to the importance of diverse representation in forming perceptions about victimhood. She argues that seeing numbers is one thing, but those numbers need to be brought to life by drawing them into scenarios to make the material more memorable.

Megan, a 28-year-old active-duty nurse in the Air Force Reserves, corroborates what Sheila suggested about the presence of female-only victimization scenarios and confirms the absence of males in these scenarios. When asked to describe what a victim of sexual assault looks like, she referred to females. When probed further, she elaborated that:

I mean it's very clear that verbally, you know, a male or a female could be victimized. But when we come to watching the scenarios, it's usually females as the victims. I can't think of a time where it was a male that was the victim.

Here, Megan clearly delineates the differences in hearing versus seeing and the role that plays in understanding. By glossing over potential male victimization and constantly referencing female-victim specific scenarios, the military is reaffirming the contradictory relationship between victimhood and military masculinity. It sends a message that female sexual violence is real sexual violence because that is the only image that is being portrayed. Therefore, the idea that military men are dominant and thus, cannot be victimized becomes concrete through these trainings. This is illustrated through Megan's statement adding that male sexual victimization is "not textbook sexual assault." The argument that male victims are not "textbook" infers that there are victim identities, presumably women, who do fit that textbook standard. Megan's statement acknowledges the influence of sexual assault training programs and military culture in constructing what "textbook sexual assault" looks like through the promotion of military masculinity combined with ideal victimhood.

This section adds to the thesis by presenting the ways in which sexual assault materials reaffirms notions of military masculinity and ideal victimhood, framing these two concepts as inherently opposite. These concepts, when applied to sexual assault, inhibit males from garnering appropriate recognition as victims. This helps us to understand where the perceptions about male sexual victimization among service members stems from, which is discussed in further detail in the final section.

Locating Military Masculinity in Perceptions of Male Victimization in Sexual Assault

The following quotes illustrate perceived bias and stigma against male victims of sexual assault based heavily on military masculinity and ideal victimhood within the military. Being sexually assaulted leads to a loss of respect and trust from fellow servicemembers caused by a perceived loss of reliability. In sum, male victims no longer fit socialized military standards of masculinity and, thus, manhood. This belief, of varying degrees, was shared by all of my participants. Just as military masculinity is internalized and sways perceptions of male victims, these perceptions are also internalized by male victims in the military, and it affects their own self-perceptions related to their status and sense of belonging as military men.

The production of military masculinity and ideal victimhood through hazing, training programming, and military messaging reinforces the belief that military men are dominant and cannot be victimized. When I asked participants about their initial feelings and attitudes about male victims of sexual assault, they applied military masculinity and reinforced beliefs about the ideal victim with very little departure from these ideas. To start, there was a shared sense of disbelief regarding male sexual victimization in the military. This included both doubt about whether or not male servicemembers could be sexually assaulted and also victim-blaming rhetoric. Sean expresses how servicemembers experience disbelief about the possibility of male victimization in a military context saying, "it's odd. How could you be a victim of sexual assault when the image of a military man is to be this strong, chiseled warrior? So, how could that happen?" This statement illustrates the internal challenge servicemembers face in an attempt to consider male victimization through the lens of military masculinity. Sean's identification of military men as "strong, chiseled warrior[s]" relates back to that warrior model of masculinity that informs military masculinity (Duncanson 2009). Inherent to the warrior model of masculinity is the normalization of violence and dominance to defeat enemies. This ideology presents a conflict for Sean in accepting the existence of male sexual victimization in the military because it assumes military men are undefeatable. Consequently, military men cannot be victims because they would fight off any potential perpetrator (O'Brien et al. 2015; Castro et al. 2015; Monteith et al. 2019; Sadler et al. 2021).

Zach echoes these messages and clearly identifies the presence of military masculinity in saying that male victims should remain silent based on the "fear of losing some of your masculinity by portraying yourself as a victim; because you can't be an alpha and a victim." When asked to elaborate, Zach simply replied, "if an alpha were to exert dominance over another man, another alpha, that alpha is a beta at that point." Speaking on this alpha-male mentality, Zach points to the importance of dominance in sexual assault and defining masculinity in the military. His use of the phrase "if an alpha were to exert dominance over another man," he is associating perpetration of sexual assault as a means to earn dominance by theoretically taking it away from another man

(victim). To that end, he identifies two contradictory identities: perpetrator (alpha) and victim (beta). This speaks to the unachievable, archetypal nature of military masculinity in that there can only be one person that is the most dominant; therefore, it pits servicemembers against each other to show and exert their dominance. Resultantly, male victims compared to “alpha[s]” no longer achieve status and dominance according to standards of military masculinity. This loss of status also points to how the achievement of military masculinity is fragile and can easily be revoked based on a hint of weakness.

Matthew, a 50-year-old retired Army sergeant, uses a similar argument positioning perpetrators of sexual assault as “alpha,” while male victims are less so. However, Matthew shifts the focus of his statement away from perpetrators and identifies the male victims’ role in sexual assault. He explains that he was under the impression that:

Male victims that had been sexually assaulted, they were in an environment with a lot of alpha males, so to speak. But they weren’t necessarily the alpha male, they were kind of a weak link... But if you look at a chain-link fence or a chain that you’re going to connect from one end to another and one of those links within the chain wasn’t welded properly, that’s the loosest or weakest part. A lot of studies came back and just said they [males] were more than often victimized because they were in an environment where they showed weakness.

In his description of male sexual assault in the military, Matthew places blame on victims by pointing to their lack of military masculinity as a reason for why they were assaulted. In this way, he argues that service members are assaulted when they show weakness or are a “weak link” compared to more dominant “alpha males.” This alludes, again, to the importance of dominance and the violent consequences associated with a lack of dominance formed through socialized competitive masculinity. Further, he also points to the role of military masculinity in glorifying and normalizing violence by saying male victims are in “an environment with a lot of alpha males” where a lot of men are vying for power and control, as if that rationalizes sexual assault. The presence of weakness and consequent feminization of military men suggests that the perpetration of sexual assault is appropriate grounded in military masculinity ideologies that value dominance and normalize violence (Duncanson 2009; Henry 2017; Zalewski 2017). This shows that the context of violence and

domination that makes up a large part of military masculinity is internalized, normalized, and perpetrated among servicemembers. Based on these internalized ideals, sexual assault of weaker “beta” males by stronger “alpha” males becomes taken for granted in the military.

This notion that “beta” males are dominated by “alpha” males through sexual assault is driven home by Antonio, who I previously introduced. Antonio uses this idea to introduce the widely shared belief that victims of sexual assault are less reliable and capable as a soldier and a leader. Antonio explains how he thinks male victims would be treated in the Army if they chose to disclose to their unit, saying:

Maybe their masculinity would be invalid. They wouldn't have the validity; their masculinity would not mean much because it was taken by another man. Or someone might be like 'how can this person be in charge of me if this person was sexually assaulted? This person is a victim of sexual assault? He was taken advantage of so how is he in charge of me?'

Antonio's assumption that a male victim's masculinity is invalidated through victimization shows the internalization of military masculinity and its role in substantiating a level of power and respect. This relates back to male positioning through the competitive performance of dominance and masculinity that was discussed in the first section of my findings. Military masculinity is constructed through ones' dominance over another or group of others. When someone has been sexually assaulted, subordination is part of the process. Thus, if a man is victimized, there is a perceived loss of dominance and masculinity by outsiders. Specifically, the implication that a victim's masculinity is “taken” so their authority is then questioned shows how military masculinity is equated to power and the presence of it, or lack thereof, impacts their standing in the military. That victim no longer maintains military masculinity because that status was taken by a seemingly more dominant perpetrator. This loss of masculinity leads people to question the victim's credibility, capability, and the legitimacy of their formal power based on the chain of command and rank in the military, just as victims of sexual assault are stigmatized based on perceived blame in their assault (Weider and Griffit 1983). This is displayed through the inquisition of a victim's leadership abilities through the question “how is he in charge of me?” Questioning the legitimacy of a victim's power, specifically by an

underling, illustrates a level of disbelief because someone who has been perceived to have lost their masculinity and dominance holds a higher position than someone who maintains that military masculinity. This reflects stigmatization wherein male victims no longer maintain their sense of belonging among fellow servicemembers. Instead, their position within units are questioned based on perceived character defects stemming from their victimization (Goffman 1963; Weider and Griffit 1983).

Just like Antonio's claim that male victims are illegitimate and less capable, Fabian explains that you have to be "physically and mentally strong in the military" and that having been victimized gives the impression that you are not strong enough to do your job. In his claim, Fabian alludes to the notion that physically and mentally strong servicemembers cannot be victimized and so, if you are, then you are weak. This relates back to the claim made by Weider and Griffit (1983) that victims of sexual assault are stigmatized based on alleged character defects, such as being weak and subordinate. This also reflects notions of ideal victimhood in that victims maintain feminine traits, such as weakness and vulnerability, and thus, male victims are perceived as feminine. As a result, male victims are perceived to be less reliable and capable in their roles within the military which values masculinity.

This notion that male victims are unreliable, and incapable was also expressed by Zach, who explains the changed group dynamic when a fellow servicemember is sexually victimized, claiming that:

We would look at it as weakness; you're weak. And if I'm in a situation where I need your help and we're deployed and an enemy is overwhelming force on me, you're useless because I can't trust you; can't trust that you're going to be able to help me and aid me in that situation.

Zach's statement elucidates the consequences of a loss of military masculinity after being sexually assaulted by pointing to physical indicators and weakness to undermine their abilities. When Zach equates victimization as a weakness and argues "you're useless because I can't trust you," he is pointing to the importance of military masculinity in forming bonds and trust in the military. This loss of military masculinity and consequent weakness is problematic since military masculinity is grounded in

the expectation to fight and defend yourself and others in combat (Duncanson 2009; Belkin 2012; Zurbriggen 2017). This new perceived inability to hold your own in battle results in a loss of trust by fellow servicemembers. This loss of trust points to that life and death context where trust is vital, and victims no longer belong due to a perceived loss of military masculinity.

Sheila furthers the notion of male victims' weakness and loss of reliability by critiquing male victims' abilities to think critically and identify threats in the military. Sheila argues that sexual victimization can put potential job promotions at risk predicated on this notion of victims being less reliable and capable in the military context. Of this, she explains:

Like they put themselves in that situation, like almost victim-blaming. How did you even allow that to happen? You put yourself in a compromising situation... Why didn't you say anything earlier before it got to this point? I think a lot of it, in my mind, goes back to their intellect of, like, why didn't you see this coming? Why didn't you do this? And then tying that intellect to maybe they are not as attentive at their job.

Similar to Zach, Sheila alludes to the idea that victims are somehow less reliable and capable to do their job since they could not protect themselves from being assaulted. Simultaneously, she engages in victim blaming since they put themselves "in a compromising situation." While Zach uses physical indicators, such as weakness, to undermine victims' abilities to protect themselves and others in dangerous situations, Sheila points to intellectual downfalls that extends from a victim's personal life into their professional life. This reflects military masculinity through the assumption that real military men would not allow themselves to be put in compromising situations and would be cunning enough to maintain their dominance in any situation. Because male victims fail to meet this expectation, they no longer meet those arbitrary standards of military masculinity and, consequently, are no longer capable of doing their jobs adequately. Sheila displays this by questioning "why didn't you see it coming" and concluding that "maybe they are not as attentive at their job."

This questioning of male victims in relation to their intellect and judgment functions again as a form of stigma (Goffman 1963; Weider and Griffit 1983). Sheila, herself, acknowledges that this line of thinking is a form of victim-blaming, yet she continues anyway. When she asks the question "how did you even allow that to happen," she is implying that a victim has a level of choice or control, and is,

therefore, to blame. Her use of victim-blaming is important because it clarifies the role of military masculinity as a prerequisite for the job. A male victim's lack of military masculinity and lack of ability to do their job by protecting themselves assumes that they could have prevented or avoided being victimized if they put in more effort. Additionally, Sheila's identity as a woman in expressing these beliefs is vital because it shows how the importance and implications of military masculinity is internalized by both men and women in the military. This points back to the role of the military in producing and reaffirming masculine ideologies separate from social and gender norms that exist outside of the military (Barnao 2019). While in broader society women are expected to value femininity, this is replaced in the military with the valuation of masculinity.

Two of my participants, John and Jackson, spoke from personal experience about their fear of the exact consequences that were described by other participants, and how this affected their self-perceptions, decisions about disclosure, and help-seeking behaviors such as accessing resources. John explains the effect of internalized military masculinity on his experience as a victim saying, "I think a man admitting he was taken advantage of is a direct conflict to his self-consideration of manhood." John's association of being "taken advantage of" as a "direct conflict" to his claim to "manhood" alludes to the importance of military masculinity in defining manhood based on the assumed ownership of dominance and strength. As a result, a perceived loss of military masculinity equates to a perceived loss of dominance, strength, and, ultimately, status as a man. Consequently, to prevent such a loss, and pointing to the internalized fear of loss of manhood, a male victim of sexual assault in the military may be less likely to disclose or report their victimization. Supporting this line of thought, neither John or Jackson chose to report their assaults or disclose what had happened to them at the time. It was not until over twenty years later that they decided to share their experiences with family and close friends.

John explains his decision to remain silent about his victimization, referring to the distinction between military masculinity and hegemonic, civilian masculinity. He identifies the military context in setting expectations for masculinity, stating "again, you're in the military, you are considered a tough

guy. You are the type that runs into a firefight, into battle.” John’s use of the phrase “you are the type that runs into a firefight, into battle” shows the heightened expectations of military masculinity versus civilian masculinity based on the context of inherent violence and war. The idea that military men should be able to handle themselves in “battle” leads to the belief that they should definitely be able to defend themselves against sexual assault.

Adding to John’s reasoning for remaining silent within the military, especially, Jackson explains the fear of being identified as a victim in the military and the stigma that would follow:

I felt nothing but shame. And I was absolutely in fear that somebody was going to know what I just did. Like I, all of a sudden, felt like it was all my fault, like I was the one responsible for that.

Jackson’s sense of shame and guilt is common amongst men and women who have experienced sexual assault (Lawrence 2016; Fiering et. al.1996; Miller et. al. 2011). However, this feeling also reflects internalized military masculinity in the way that military men feel as if they should be able to take care of themselves more so than women or civilian men. Another component of Jackson’s statement is the fear of stigmatization and potential consequences in disclosure. The phrase “I was absolutely in fear that somebody was going to know what I just did” speaks to the consideration of inevitable stigma and the loss of credibility that he would face if anybody found out, as expressed by other participants. Moreover, Jackson’s framing of his experience not as an assault, but rather as “what I just did” echoes the sentiment that as a military man, he should have had control over the situation and his lack of dominance in that moment puts the blame on him.

Jackson’s described internalization of stigma influenced by military masculinity further impacts his perception regarding the severity of his assault. Specifically, Jackson attempts to minimize and trivialize his assault. After explaining the manner in which he was sexually assaulted, Jackson asked me, “I know that for a woman being raped has probably got to be way more horrifying than what happened to me, right?” This question reflects the internalization of characteristics of the ideal victim through Jackson’s hesitancy to equate male rape to female rape, or “real rape.” His comparison of a

hypothetical female rape as “way more horrifying” than his own assault reflects his attempt to distance himself from the victim identity and position himself back in a place of power.

CHAPTER 6

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this study, I examined perceptions of male sexual victimization within the U.S. military. Specifically, I aimed to answer the question: How are the perceptions and beliefs about male victims of sexual assault among U.S. military servicemembers shaped through the production of masculinity within the U.S. military? Drawing from 21 in-depth, semi-structured qualitative interviews with veteran and active duty servicemembers, findings reflect themes about the military as a total institution and the effect of military masculinity on perceptions about male sexual victimization and perpetuation of the ideal victim. This research fills the gap in literature concerning the presence of socialized masculine ideologies found within perceptions about male victims of sexual assault in the military context.

Findings consistently pointed to the power that the military has as a total institution in breaking down individuals and molding service members into mass-produced soldiers that reflect military masculinity (Goffman 1961). Influenced by the hypermasculine culture in the U.S. military constructed through the context of war and the normalization of violence, participants' statements reflected the internalized expectations to conform and enact military masculinity through male positioning and practices that glorify violence, such as hazing. Building on research conducted by Barnao (2019), this study shows how service members are barred from interaction outside of the closed military environment to ensure that service members adhere to socially constructed norms, values, and procedures that exist separate from broader society. My findings reflect the isolation and seclusion experienced by service members through their description of the all-encompassing nature of military life, and work in agreement with existing literature that ties this solitude to imposed military socialization (Barnao 2019). The adoption of military norms and practices are coerced, and socialization is forced through training and punishment (Goffman 1961; Belkin 2012; Hale 2012; Schmidt 2015). Participants voiced the pressure they felt to participate in hazing through group pressure and faced consequences like social ostracization, stigma, and potential retaliation relating to

job security. The pressure to enact military masculinity in this way illustrates the loss of agency service members experience in the military through coerced socialization and conformity, while being held accountable by fellow service members and the military as an institution.

The military as a total institution also sheds light on the prevalence and attitude concerning rates of sexual assault in the military. Scholars suggest that some environments, more than others, tend to foster cultures that encourage and promote the perpetration of sexual assault. These cultures can be identified through their adherence to notions of hypermasculinity, acceptance of violence, dehumanization, and a lack of empathy, all of which are socialized in the military (Murnen et al. 2002; Baaz and Stern 2009; Duncanson 2009; Zurbriggen 2010; O'Toole et al. 2014; Castro et al. 2015; Khan et al. 2020). Looking at conversations around sexual assault in the military, findings alluded to a code of silence shared among service members in regard to cases of sexual assault. This code of silence, which was supported through extant literature, is maintained institutionally to protect the narrative that the military is an organization consisting of order, cohesion, and strength (O'Toole et al. 2014; Castro et al. 2015; Monteith et al. 2019). In turn, such silence removes the threat of consequences for perpetrators. This pattern of turning a blind eye also impacts how sexual assault training is perceived by service members, influencing the effectiveness and comprehensiveness of training programs.

Many participants indicated that sexual assault training programs were insignificant in the military, and nobody really took them seriously. This laissez-faire attitude about training, combined with stereotypical and limited representation of victim identities, paints a concerning image regarding the effectiveness of the military training programs. Holland et al. (2014) studied the perceived effectiveness of the military Sexual Assault Prevention and Response Program (SAPR) and found that service members do not receive adequate sexual assault training due to the failure of current programs to address root causes of sexual assault and properly emphasize the scope of the problem. My findings support this notion as many of my participants discussed how sexual assault training scenarios depict non-military contexts and reflect conceptions of ideal victimhood, constantly

featuring vulnerable women assaulted by strangers in a bar. Participants expressed that these images send a message that female sexual assault is “textbook sexual assault,” which influences how they view potential sexual assault that does not fit within that narrow definition, such as those concerning male victims. Two of my participants, Fabian and Francis, both describe images of sexual assault victimization that are advertised in the military, including strange male perpetrators and vulnerable female victims.

This, exactly, was an issue when participants described their reactions toward male victims of sexual assault in the military. The effect of forced socialization of military masculinity, detailing that military men are strong, dominant, hypermasculine warriors, and the perpetuation of the ideal victim in training materials led to the stigmatization of male victims. Goffman (1963) describes stigma as a process in which individuals are discredited and othered based on a perceived character defect. Victims of sexual assault, specifically, experience stigma relating to their apparent blame for their victimization, resulting in snap judgements based on societal norms. Because the military is a total institution and norms and values within this setting are inherently unique and isolated, judgements about male victims in the military are grounded in constructions of military masculinity (Goffman 1961; Weider and Griffit 1983; Lawrence 2016; Robertson 2018). Because military masculinity is substantiated through the presence of dominance and the ability to protect oneself and others in battle, male victims of sexual assault seemingly lose their claim to masculinity (Duncanson 2009; Belkin 2012; Zurbriggen 2017). As a result, male victims’ abilities and position in the military are questioned based on a supposed loss of masculinity, replaced by feminine traits such as weakness. This weakness translates to a loss of reliability and capability as a service member and potential leader based on victim blaming, leading to stigma by fellow service members which threatens victims’ abilities to advance in their careers through institutional consequences like denial of promotions.

The stigma affecting male victims of sexual assault in the military is also founded in male rape myths that perpetuate the false beliefs that only gay men are sexually assaulted, men cannot be forced to have sex against their will, and men are less affected by sexual assault than women (Weiss

2010; Burks 2011; Javaid 2015; Castro et al. 2015; O'Brien et al. 2015; Hlavka 2016). These rape myths are often internalized by victims, which affect their likelihood to identify as victims, disclose sexual assault, and impact their self-perceptions of manhood and belonging (Weiss 2010; O'Brien et al. 2015; Monteith et al. 2019). This was apparent through the discussion of decision-making with John and Jackson, two participants who had been sexually assaulted in the military. John and Jackson both spoke about how their victimization conflicted with their self-perception of manhood and claim to masculinity in the military, reflecting internalized male rape myths, ideal victimhood, and notions of military masculinity. They felt guilt and shame that they were unable to defend themselves from being assaulted and kept silent about their victimizations out of fear of stigma and disbelief.

Ultimately, these reactions to male rape and snap judgements or perceptions about male victims, and by male victims, are informed by the socialization of military masculinity and reinforcement of the ideal victim evident in every corner of the military. These traditional masculine ideologies are supported through tradition and passed on through generations of service members, creating a never-ending cycle of glorified violence. The violent culture, enforced through hazing practices and forced competitiveness are upheld through a code of silence that further harms victims and non-victims of sexual assault in the military. This code of silence and promotion of military masculinity encourage the persistence of violence and stigma, which subordinate service members and help keep them in line. As we can see through these findings, the construction, production, and reinforcement of military masculinity through systematic institutional efforts create these collectively held harsh perceptions about male victims of sexual assault.

Participants' statements reflect interpretations of male sexual victimization that reinforce ideal victimhood and the normalization of sexual violence based on ideals of hegemonic military masculinity. Findings show that these beliefs are impacted by sexual assault training and military culture that values violence and domination. Additionally, these beliefs about male sexual victimization and masculinity reflect societal norms that are adapted in the military. This makes training and reform efforts difficult to address because there are many factors that impact the

perpetuation of military sexual assault and perceptions about male sexual victimization. Findings suggest that current efforts fail to address the root causes of military sexual assault while the hypermasculine culture that fosters violence is largely ignored. This is problematic because it contributes to underreporting of male sexual victimization and encourages the ongoing cycle of violence and the stigmatization of victimhood. My findings support arguments for the abolishment of current sexual assault training programs utilized in the military, replaced with a more inclusive curriculum that critiques the culture of masculinity that promotes violence and normalizes diverse victim identities (Holland et al. 2014).

Limitations

There were four main limitations I encountered during this research process. First, I was not fully able to understand the socializing nature of the military based solely on interviews. This research would, additionally, benefit from observations. In the future, I would consider doing a more in-depth ethnographic study using observations, but during the Coronavirus pandemic that was not possible. Another limitation to this study is that participants are responding retrospectively, some recalling memories from over fifty years prior, which presents issues with memory and accuracy of events. Notably, however, I intentionally did not limit age because the historical presence and framing of sexual assault and male victimization was of interest to the current study. Additionally, the majority of my participants were retired from the military, so training implications could be different from those experienced by a heavier active-duty sample. Many active-duty service members were hesitant to participate because they were afraid of potential backlash from the military for participating or they were worried about how they may represent the military in a negative light.

Finally, differences in experience based on racial and ethnic considerations are missing from my analysis. While I asked questions about race and ethnicity throughout the interviews, participants often replied that race was not a significant factor in their experience and that racial tensions did not exist in the military. This hesitancy to speak about race and observations that the military existed free of racial tension illustrates how the U.S. military is an institution that reflects the white supremacist

capitalist heteropatriarchy that exists in society, where interlocking systems of domination benefit white individuals and keep them oblivious to struggles and discrimination faced by other racial and ethnic groups (Hooks 1984). This was a finding that I was unable to address in my analysis due to the limited scope of my study and limited racial diversity in my participants.

Future Directions

Based on my findings, future research addressing some or all of the limitations I identify above are beneficial to better represent the current impacts of military socialization and training programs. Gaining direct access to this population through additional observation, while difficult, would likely eliminate blind spots influenced by hesitancy to share traditions with outsiders. This may be an avenue of research that would be better conducted by military personnel with an insider status.

Another avenue of research should focus on perspectives from higher-ranking leaders that conduct SAPR trainings and are responsible for carrying out reporting to better understand how military socialization influences decision-making regarding the investigative process and potential retaliation. Little is known about the role of higher-ranking officials, and how they may deter or encourage victims from garnering resources and justice. The back end of this process, following socialization and victimization, would be an interesting research pursuit.

APPENDIX A

RESEARCH FLYER

RESEARCH STUDY SEEKING PARTICIPANTS

★ ARE YOU CURRENTLY OR HAVE YOU EVER SERVED IN THE U.S. MILITARY? ★

This study will examine the perceptions that military service members have toward male victims of sexual assault.

Eligibility includes:

- Must be 18 +
- Must either currently serve or previously served in the U.S. military

Study includes a brief sociodemographic survey and a semi structured interview.

Participation will take between an hour to an hour and a half.

If interested please contact Aspen Dyer
 adyer@csu.fullerton.edu
 (714) 869-1430

Interviews will take place on Zoom or via phone currently. In-person meetings may be available as circumstances surrounding COVID-19 change.

Participation is completely confidential.

APPENDIX B

PARTICIPANT TABLE

NAME	GENDER	AGE	BRANCH	STATUS	TIME OF SERVICE	RANK
BILL	MALE	80	ARMY	VETERAN	4 YEARS	E3
MATTHEW	MALE	50	ARMY	RETIRED	26 YEARS	E7
SEAN	MALE	46	ARMY	VETERAN	4 YEARS	E5
ZACH	MALE	41	ARMY	VETERAN	4 YEARS	E4
ROSA	FEMALE	38	ARMY	VETERAN	8 YEARS	E5
ASHLEY	FEMALE	36	ARMY	VETERAN	5 YEARS	E4
ANTONIO	MALE	25	ARMY	ACTIVE DUTY	4 YEARS +	E6
SHEILA	FEMALE	27	ARMY/AIR FORCE	NATIONAL GUARD	7 YEARS +	E6
DAVID	MALE	61	AIR FORCE	RETIRED	22 YEARS	E8
BRITTANY	FEMALE	47	AIR FORCE	VETERAN	10 YEARS	E5
FABIAN	MALE	35	AIR FORCE	MEDICALLY RETIRED	4.5 YEARS	O3
FRANCIS	MALE	33	AIR FORCE	VETERAN	10 YEARS	E5
MEGAN	FEMALE	28	AIR FORCE	RESERVE	10 YEARS +	E8
CARLOS	MALE	28	AIR FORCE	ACTIVE DUTY	8 YEARS +	E5
KYLE	MALE	56	NAVY	RETIRED	24 YEARS	E7
JOHN	MALE	53	NAVY	VETERAN	10 YEARS	E5
ANDREW	MALE	52	NAVY	RETIRED	20 YEARS	E7
MAX	MALE	23	NAVY	ACTIVE DUTY	3.5 YEARS +	E3
THOMAS	MALE	42	MARINE CORPS	RETIRED	20 YEARS	CWO3
ALAN	MALE	22	MARINE CORPS	VETERAN	4 YEARS	E4
JACKSON	MALE	67	COAST GUARD	VETERAN	4 YEARS	E4

APPENDIX C

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Study Title: Examining the Role of Masculinity and Stigma in U.S. Military Members' Perceptions of Male Victims of Sexual Assault

Protocol Number: HSR-20-21-265

Researchers: Aspen Dyer- M.A. Candidate, Department of Sociology, California State University, Fullerton.

Faculty Advisor: Dr. Thacker Thomas- Associate Professor, Department of Sociology, California State University, Fullerton.

You are being asked to take part in a research study carried out by Aspen Dyer. This consent form explains the research study and your part in it if you decide to join the study. Please read the form carefully, taking as much time as you need. Ask the researcher to explain anything you don't understand. You can decide not to join the study. If you join the study, you can change your mind later and leave the study at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of services or benefits if you decide to not take part in the study.

What is this study about?

This research study is being conducted to examine the perceptions that U.S. military service members have toward male victims of sexual assault. You are being asked to participate in this study because you: (1) are either currently in the U.S. military or have retired from the U.S. military; (2) are eighteen years of age or older.

Taking part in this study will take between 1-1.5 hours. You cannot participate if you are under the age of 18 and have never participated in the U.S. military.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

If you take part in the study, you will be asked to spend approximately an hour to an hour and a half in an interview with Aspen Dyer. You will begin by filling out a short socio-demographic survey that will take approximately five minutes to complete. Survey questions will inquire about age, gender, amount of time spent in military, and military branch. The remaining time will be allotted to the interview. Interview questions are designed to examine the perceptions that U.S. service members have toward male victims of sexual assault based on their understandings of masculinity. Interview sample questions include: *What was your experience like during formal training in the military? In a few words could you describe what you feel the culture of the military encompasses? How has your view of the world changed or stayed the same since you joined the military? What kind of policies do you know of that address sexual assault in the military?*

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

There is no direct benefit to you from being in this study. However, participation in this study may help advance the understanding of how institutions such as the U.S. military impact the perceptions of male victims of sexual assault. Sexual assault is an ongoing issue in U.S. society and male victims have been increasingly more recognized in the social sphere. If different experiences within institutions impact perceptions of male victims, then it is crucial to examine how and why this occurs. Additionally, the findings of this study may contribute to the gap in literature about male victimhood

and the U.S. military. The findings from this study may ultimately result in policy recommendations or interventions that the U.S. military may adopt surrounding gender and sexual assault awareness education programs.

Are there any risks to me if I am in this study?

The potential risks from taking part in this study are distress or discomfort associated with the sensitive nature of the subject matter and related questions. In order to minimize the risks associated with this study the researcher will remind the participant that participation is completely voluntary and they can refuse to answer any questions that cause discomfort. The interviews will be audio recorded and transcribed with permission from the participant. The researcher will make every effort to maintain confidentiality through the use of pseudonyms for participant identity and identifiable locations. All data resulting from this study will be stored in a password protected location that only the researcher and her faculty advisor have access to.

Will my information be kept anonymous or confidential?

The data for this study will be kept confidential to the extent allowed by law. No published results will identify you, and your name will not be associated with the findings. Under certain circumstances, information that identifies you may be released for internal and external reviews of this project. Any data resulting from this study will be stored in a secure, password protected computer with limited access. Specifically, data will only be accessible by Aspen Dyer and her faculty advisor, Dr. Devon Thacker Thomas. The results of this study may be published or presented at educational sites, but the identities of research participants will remain anonymous. The data for this study will be kept for a minimum of 3 years after completion of the study, but may be kept indefinitely. This data will be used for future educational use, presentations, or publications, and thus must be kept in order to support further research.

- Interview data will be coded and a key will be kept separately on a password protected computer.
- All interview conversations will be between the participant and researcher only.
- All California State University employees who are identified as Limited and General Reporters are mandated to report under California's Child Abuse and Neglect Reporting Act ("CANRA"). Whenever such an identified CSU employee, in his/her professional capacity or within the scope of his/her employment or research activities, has knowledge of or observes a person under the age of 18 years whom the employee knows, or reasonably suspects, to have been the victim of child abuse or neglect, the employee must report the incident to the appropriate authorities.
- If participant agrees, audio recordings will be used throughout the interview process.

Are there any costs or payments for being in this study?

There will be no costs to you for taking part in this study. You will not receive money or any other form of compensation for taking part in this study.

Who can I talk to if I have questions?

If you have questions about this study or the information in this form, please contact the researcher Aspen Dyer. If you have questions about your rights as a research participant, or would like to report a concern or complaint about this study, please contact Dr. Thacker Thomas at xxx-xxx-xxxx, or email at xxxxxxxx@fullerton.edu. Additionally, the Institutional Review Board at xxx-xxx-xxxx, or e-mail xxx@fullerton.edu.

What are my rights as a research study volunteer?

Your participation in this research study is completely voluntary. You may choose not to be a part of this study. There will be no penalty to you if you choose not to take part. You may choose not to answer specific questions or to stop participating at any time.

What does my signature on this consent form mean?

Your signature on this form means that:

- You understand the information given to you in this form
- You have been able to ask the researcher questions and state any concerns
- The researcher has responded to your questions and concerns
- You believe you understand the research study and the potential benefits and risks that are involved.

Statement of Consent

I have carefully read and/or I have had the terms used in this consent form and their significance explained to me. By signing below, I agree that I am at least 18 years of age and agree to participate in this project. You will be given a copy of this signed and dated consent form to keep.

Name of Participant (please print) _____

Signature of Participant _____ Date _____

Signature of Investigator _____ Date _____

If you are requesting permission to audio or videotape; create a second signature line for that. An individual could conceivably be willing to participate, but not to be included in an audio or videotape.

Your signature below indicates that you are giving permission to audio/video tape your responses.

Signature of Participant _____ Date _____

APPENDIX D

SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC SURVEY

Project: U.S. Military Perceptions of Male Victims of Sexual Assault
Researcher: Aspen Dyer- Sociology MA Candidate, CSU Fullerton
Contacts: Aspen Dyer & Devon Thacker Thomas, Ph.D.

Participant # _____

1. Indicate your gender

_____ Female

_____ Male

_____ Other: _____

_____ Prefer not to answer

2. Indicate your age

3. What is your highest level of education?

_____ Less than high school

_____ High school diploma/GED

_____ Some college

_____ Associate Degree

_____ Bachelor's degree

_____ Masters or Ph.D.

4. What is your current military service status?

_____ Active Duty

_____ Reserve

_____ National Guard

_____ Retired

_____ Other: _____

5. What branch of military have you previously or currently served in?

6. How long did you or have you served in the military as of today?

7. What is the highest rank you have achieved in the military to date?

8. Please circle which statistic you believe is most accurate regarding the frequency that males are victims of sexual assault.

1 in 3 1 in 6 1 in 15 1 in 30 1 in 90 Don't know/Not sure

9. What type of awareness (campaigns, courses, conversations with others, etc.) about sexual assault do you see in the military?

10. Do any sexual assault awareness campaigns or messaging that you see/hear about in the military mention male victims? If so, please describe them.

APPENDIX E

INTERVIEW GUIDE

Project: U.S. Military Perceptions of Male Victims of Sexual Assault

Researcher: Aspen Dyer- Sociology MA Candidate, CSU Fullerton

Contacts: Aspen Dyer & Devon Thacker Thomas, Ph.D.

- **Primary research question:** How has the socialization of masculine ideologies in the military affected perceptions that U.S. military members have about male victims of sexual assault?
 - **Secondary research question:** Do male and female service members differ in their perceptions of male victims of sexual assault, and why?
 - **Secondary research question:** What is the role of the military in shaping definitions of masculinity and gender and framing sexual violence, which ultimately shapes perceptions of male victims of sexual assault?

Introduction

- How are you?
- Thank you for participating
- During this interview we are going to discuss a couple of different aspects of sexual assault as related to boys and men. As a reminder, you can decline answering any questions that make you uncomfortable.

Initial Info and Training

- Tell me a little bit about your military experience.
 - How did you become interested in the military?
 - Why did you decide to join X branch?
- What is your job/rank within the military?
 - When thinking of your daily work environment, what types of people most often work with you? What do they look like? (Age, race, gender)
 - Are your superiors primarily men or women?

Where have you been stationed in the military?

In a few words, could you describe the culture of the military?

What does 'respect' look like to you in the military? How about when you first enlisted vs. now?

How has your view of the world changed (or stayed the same) since you joined the military?

- What are some examples?

What was your experience like during formal training (such as basic training, but also any continued training) in the military?

- Are men and women together in these programs? Why/why not?
- What types of specialized topics were discussed, if any?
- What aspects of training were emphasized most?
- So it sounds like there was defined goals within the formal socialization within the military (basic).

Were there any ways you experienced informal sanctioning? Or just messaging or things informally agreed upon within your team?

- Any rituals or traditions you experienced or heard about?
- What did you value together as a team?

Gender

- Can you tell me about your earliest memory when you realized you were a boy? Did this shift as you grew up?
- In your opinion, what does it mean to be a man in our society? What does it mean to be a woman in our society?
 - Any specific traits or experiences that you think are important to have?
- What does it mean to be a man in the military? Are there any differences compared to civilians that stand out to you?
 - How/where do you see these standards reflected in the military?
 - i.e- cliques, messaging from superiors, traditions, etc.
 - How does this relate to your earliest memory of being a boy?

Describe some typical characteristics you would expect of the men with whom you work?

- Is there any overlap with traits associated with masculinity?
 - Sexuality, work ethic?
- Are there any major differences between expectations of men/women?

How has your view of gender norms and sexuality changed since you joined the military?

- Examples? (importance of traditional gender roles, [i.e: men make \$ & are in control, women stay at home] beliefs about LGBTQ+, etc.)

What are the differences in the way male and female service members interact or are treated by coworkers?

- Peer groups, group cohesion?

How do you feel your gender shapes the way you view your role in the military?

- How about in your family or with friends?
- How does this relate to your earliest memory of being a boy?

Male Victimization

- Can you tell me what you envision when you hear “crime victim?”
 - Who comes to mind? What do they look like?
 - What types of crimes?
- Can you tell me what you envision when you hear “sexual assault?”
 - What does the victim or victims look like? Who are the perpetrators? Context?
 - Who you think are most likely the perpetrators of sexual assault? Why?
 - Do you think this type of person can be sexually assaulted themselves?

How likely do you believe it is for boys/men to be sexually assaulted?

- Why?
- Why do you think it happens?
 - Why do you think you don't have that personal knowledge?

Describe your initial thoughts and feelings regarding male victims of sexual assault.

- What types of influences have shaped your feelings or attitudes about what it means to be a male victim of sexual assault?

In what scenarios do you think men are sexually assaulted?

What kind of training have you had about sexual assault in the military?

- How much do you feel sexual assault training is prioritized?
- If you could design your own sexual assault curriculum or training, how would you change it from the current training?
 - What is important to you in these programs?
 - What scenarios would you use for female victims? What about males?

What kind of policies do you know of that address sexual assault in the military?

- Are these policies generally enforced/discussed?
- What are your thoughts on any policies or training associated with sexual assault in the military?

How do you think cases of sexual assault should be handled within the military?

- From your experience, is this what happens?

From your understanding, what are the differences of sexual assault in the military versus in civilian life?

How would you feel about sexual assault (specifically with male victims) that take place in the military versus civilian life?

- How does the setting of the military affect your perceptions of sexual assault?

Typically, when we think of perpetrators of sexual assault we think of this strong, dominant man.

How do you think this is explained in terms of male on male sexual assault in the military where the victim and perpetrator are likely strong and dominant? How does that happen?

How do you feel you would handle a situation of sexual assault?

- What kind of emotions do you think you would feel and why?
- Would you take any steps to report an assault?

- i.e- reporting, disclosing to family/friends, going to hospital for rape-kit, seeking therapy, remaining silent/not disclosing to anyone, etc.

In your opinion, what differences, if any, should be taken into account when a case of sexual assault involves a female victim versus a male victim?

- What reasons would account for the differences?

What experiences or considerations do you think male victims of sexual assault have when considering options of reporting?

- Do you think males are more or less likely to report an assault in the military? Why?
- How do you think, if at all, the male experience differs from the female in terms of reporting/seeking help?

Closing

- We covered a lot today. Is there anything else that you might like to add that I have not asked you about?
- Is there anyone else you think I should speak to who would be interested and willing to meet with me?
- Can I contact you again for clarification of any follow up questions I may have?

APPENDIX F

RESEARCH ASSISTANT CONFIDENTIALITY FORM

RESEARCH ASSISTANT CONFIDENTIALITY AGREEMENT

I, _____, agree to assist the primary investigator with this study by editing interview transcription. I agree to maintain full confidentiality when performing these tasks. Specifically, I agree to:

1. Keep all research information shared with me confidential by not discussing or sharing the information in any form or format (e.g., disks, tapes, transcripts) with anyone other than the primary investigator.
2. Hold in strictest confidence the identification of any individual that may be revealed during the course of performing the research tasks.
3. Not make copies of any raw data in any form or format (e.g., disks, tapes, transcripts), unless specifically requested to do so by the primary investigator.
4. Keep all raw data that contains identifying information in any form or format (eg., disks, tapes, transcripts) secure while it is in my possession. This includes:
 - Keeping all digitized raw data in computer password-protected files and other raw data in a locked file.
 - Closing any computer programs and documents of the raw data when temporarily away from the computer.
 - Permanently deleting any email communication containing the data.
 - Using closed headphones when transcribing recordings.
5. Give all raw data in any form or format (e.g., disks, tapes, transcripts) to the primary investigator when I have completed the research tasks.
6. Destroy all research information in any form or format that is not returnable to the primary investigator (e.g., information stored on my computer hard drive) upon completion of the research tasks.

Printed Name of Research Assistant: _____

Address: 1135 Kent Ct. Dixon, CA. 95620

Signature of Research Assistant: _____ Date: _____

Printed Name of Primary Investigator: _____ Date: _____

Signature of Primary Investigator: _____ Date: _____

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